

Legal overview Human Genetics and Genomics: United Kingdom

[WP2 – Human Genetics and Genomics]

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Executive Summary

Goal(s)

The aim of this report is to navigate the regulatory framework of legal and human rights requirements regarding human genetics and genomics in the United Kingdom (UK). The aim is twofold. First, this report provides an overview of the UK legislation on human genetics and genomics in a brief and concise manner, including gene editing, testing and screening. Second, this report identifies and presents the relevant legal gaps, concerns, attitudes and challenges as raised and articulated in the UK legal system.

Approach

An interdisciplinary approach was adopted to address the questions of genetics and genomics in the UK legal order. A large volume of legal literature, resources and databases was reviewed to understand and delineate the legal status and provisions governing genetics and genomics in the UK. Moreover, given the technical and sectoral complexity of this task, we reviewed the literature produced by scientific bodies, regulatory and advisory bodies, such as the Nuffield Council on Bioethics, for a deeper understanding of the conceptualisation, regulation, and applications of genetics and genomics as depicted both in the legal and scientific debate.

Moreover, to fulfil this task we reviewed regulatory structures, public and ethical debates, attitudes, perceptions and trends regarding genetics and genomics practices in the UK. We conducted research in databases, such as Westlaw and Practical Law, and reviewed academic literature, official statistics, and guidance documents. The method used to prepare this report was desktop research.

Main Findings

Our research, analysis, and findings suggest that human genetics and genomics are heavily regulated in the UK. The UK has a longstanding regulatory framework and tradition regarding genetics and genomics and their clinical and research applications. This framework is based both on national and European legislation and does not include an overarching framework for the discussed topics. Instead of a comprehensive framework regulating genetics and genomics in a uniform manner across the UK, there is a fragmented legal framework. Indeed, the UK framework, as presented below, is characterised by a piecemeal and sectorial approach to genetics and genomics contingent on the type and purpose of activity (i.e., public health, biomedical research). Whereas the legal framework is quite permissive in terms of human genetic research under the appropriate safeguards, interfering with human genes for clinical purposes is heavily restricted. This reflects the fears of adverse effects if such uses are not heavily regulated and the commitment to safeguarding fundamental rights, such as the right to life, dignity and that no one should be subject to torture or inhuman or degrading treatment.

In this context, regulatory bodies play an important role in regulating and monitoring genetics and genomics practices to ensure that legal and ethical assessments are carried out and that any activity is scientifically and ethically sound. This framework has not thwarted scientific progress and initiatives. On the contrary, the power to license such activities has been vested with the competent authorities, which have been proactive and responsive to the need for scientific development and which enjoy a wide margin of discretion through the provided licensing schemes. Furthermore, genetics and genomics are highly debated in the UK at the policy and academic level. Indeed, various public consultations, market research studies, surveys and the way the applicable legislation has been

developed in the UK have set the necessary conditions for educating the public, which seems informed and progressive.¹ According to a recent survey, the UK public seems aware of the interests at stake and is cautiously optimistic about the use DNA sequencing, gene therapy and genome editing. The UK public is rather positive regarding the use of genetics and genomics technologies for human health purposes, whereas it opposes to using such technologies for cosmetic changes and human enhancement.²

Our research was mainly based on consultation papers, governmental guidance, and reports issued by advisory and regulatory bodies. Regarding the available resources, there is limited available legal literature tailored to present and address the legal questions about genetics and genomics in the UK as set out in this SIENNA task. Additionally, the prospect of the forthcoming exit of the UK from the European Union ('Brexit') has further contributed to legal uncertainty in the UK, where there is not clear and definite guidance and information on the future of the UK regulation in the life sector and research.

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¹ Federation of European Academies of Medicine, "Human Genome Editing in the EU", 10 March 2017, pp. 23. <http://www.interacademies.org/File.aspx?id=31273>

² Royal Society, "UK public cautiously optimistic about genetic technologies", 07 March 2018. <https://royalsociety.org/news/2018/03/genetic-technologies/>

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Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
3Rs	Replacement, Reduction and Refinement
ABI	Association of British Insurers
ASA	Advertising Standards Authority
ASPA	Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986
BBSRC	Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council
Charter	Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union
CoE	Council of Europe
CVS	Chorionic Villus Sampling
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GM	Genetically Modified
GT	Genetic testing
GTAC	The Gene Therapy Advisory Committee
HFEA	Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority
HRA	Health Research Authority
HSC	Health and Social Care in Northern Ireland
HTA	Human Tissue Authority
IVD	In Vitro Diagnostics
IVF	In Vitro Fertilization
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
NHS	National Health Service
NIPD	Non-Invasive Prenatal Diagnostic
NIPT	Non-Invasive Prenatal Testing
NSC	National Screening Committee
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OFT	Office of Fair Trading
PGT	Preimplantation genetic testing
PTT	Pre-implantation Tissue Typing
REC	Research Ethics Committee
UK	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

Table 2 Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Admixed embryo	Admixed embryo: As defined in section 4A(6) of Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990 as amended
Brexit	Brexit: Exit of the UK from the European Union
Genetic Test	A genetic test: is an assay performed to obtain genetic information (directly on DNA or even on other molecules (RNA, proteins), which by extension could give us genetic information.
Genetic Testing	<p>Genetic testing is usually offered to individual patients based on specific individual need on a one-on-one basis (diagnostic testing, prenatal testing, etc³). An assay (a genetic test) would be conducted after the clinician has decided to prescribe the test to the specific patient in question.</p> <p>Genetic testing is a type of medical test that identifies changes in chromosomes, genes, or proteins. The results of a genetic test can confirm or rule out a suspected genetic condition or help determine a person's chance of developing or passing on a genetic disorder.⁴ Genetic testing could be accessed through a health care provider as part of clinical medical care, or as a service or product offered directly to consumers. Issues genetic testing raises relate to access rights, protection of integrity, medical oversight when these tests are being offered, as well as genetic counselling, and quality.</p> <p>Other questions that relate to genetic testing emerge in the area of advertising and the use of genetic information. In regard to advertising such issues as, for example, whether genetic testing providers are or are not allowed to advertise their offered genetic tests emerge (contrast with a distinction being made for advertising prescription and non-prescription drugs).⁵ In regard to genetic information, such issues as who can access one's genetic information, and how this information could be used for different purposes, for example, life insurance. One of key issues that emerges in this regard is discrimination relating to one's genome.</p>
Genetic Screening	Genetic screening can have a few different meanings that differ based on subtle nuances and contexts, but in general, we contrast genetic screening from genetic testing because screening is offered to an entire group of people (not specific individuals). In particular screening cases, like

³ <https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/uses>

⁴ US National Library of Medicine, "What is genetic testing," 20 Nov 2018. <https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/genetic-testing>

⁵ See Kalokairinou, Louiza, Pascal Borry, Heidi Carmen Howard, "Regulating the advertising of genetic tests in Europe: a balancing act", *Journal of Medical Genetics*, Volume 54, Issue 10, pp. 651-656.

	<p>newborn screening, for example, the screening programme follows public health frameworks (as opposed to genetic testing which is not a public health programme but within a clinical specialty; in countries where public health programmes don't differ so strongly from clinical practice. Differences between public health programmes and clinical (one patient at a time) programmes could mean differences in how we approach consent and the obligatory nature of any programme). Other than the "group/population" aim of screening programmes, screening programmes can vary hugely in different ways: population/group targeted (population wide? Certain people/mothers at higher risks as a group?) etc..</p>
Gene Editing/Genome Editing	<p>Gene editing is a relatively recent term used for the description of modifying DNA (recombinant DNA technology or similar terms overlap in some fashion); the term gene editing has come along with the advent of particularly powerful and accurate tools like CRISPR-Cas9 (which is a tool that helps to change DNA). Gene editing can also be referred to as genome modification, which is more holistic as a concept, but addresses the same ideas; it includes not only changing individual DNA in one location but also many changes throughout the genome. One can edit genes in somatic cells (which are not inherited) or one could edit genes in gametes or germline cells which are inherited and would pass down, in theory, DNA modifications/edits to future generations.</p> <p>The term human genome germline modification includes the modification of one or many bits of DNA in an inheritable human cell. Many authors also include the replacement of mitochondria from one embryo to another as a type of germline modification, though this can be argued as (not) being very distinct from DNA modification. For comparison with other studies, we will include it in this SIENNA study.</p>

Table 3 List of national legislation

Abortion Act 1967
Amendment Regulations 2012 (SI 2012/3039)
Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986
British Nationality (Proof of Paternity) Regulations 2006
Consumer Protection from Unfair Trading Regulations 2008
Criminal Justice Act (Northern Ireland) 1945
Environmental Protection Act 1990
Equality Act 2010
European Union (Withdrawal) Act 2018.
Family Law Act 1986
Family Law Reform Act 1969
Health and Social Care Act 2008 (Regulated Activities) Regulations 2014
Human Fertilisation and Embryology (Mitochondrial Donation) Regulations 2015

Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990
Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 2008
Human Reproductive Cloning Act 2001
Human Rights Act 1998
Human Tissue (Scotland) Act 2006
Human Tissue Act 2004
Medical Devices Regulations 2002
Medicines for Human Use (Clinical Trials) Regulations 2004
Person Act 1861
Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984
Protection of Freedoms Act 2012

Part I

1. National legal system in context

1.1 An overview of the UK legal system

The United Kingdom (UK) is more a unitary than a federal state.⁶ Great Britain comprises England, Scotland and Wales. England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland have their own laws and institutions.⁷ However, this fragmentation is reduced by two factors. First, there is a common legislation that applies to the whole UK in some areas and disciplines. Second, the membership of the UK to the European Union has led to a slow, still incomplete consolidation of a few areas of law. Given the plethora and diversity of legal acts and institutions across these territories, we refer to the general provisions, namely the ones covering England and Wales and we specifically refer to the other territories only when their provisions significantly deviate from the general ones.

In the UK, rules of constitutional rank share the same sources as other laws. Its (unwritten) constitution primarily draws from four sources: statute law, common law, parliamentary conventions, and works of authority, namely literature produced by constitutional theorists that are considered to be authoritative guides to the UK constitution. Common law differs from statute law. The UK is a common law system, as opposed to the continental civil law systems. With regard to Scotland, it is worth mentioning that its legal system is not a genuine common law system, but a mixed one, under the influence of Roman law.

Common law is intertwined with the notion of precedent, namely the body of law derived from judicial decisions of courts and similar tribunals. Precedent is a formal source of law based on the justifications that judges provide for their judgements and the principles they apply.⁸ It is independent and distinctive to legislation. In this context, administrative quasi-legislation, such as guidance and codes of practice issued by governmental departments and agencies, further reflect the need for a compressive legal system and are important legal sources, although soft law.⁹

Regarding the relationship between international and national law, the UK follows the dualist legal tradition, according to which international law is legally binding only if transposed into the national legal order. In practice, international law is not directly applicable domestically, but it must be incorporated into national law by legislation to apply. 'This is a constitutional requirement and until

⁶ White, Robin M., Ian D. Willock, and Hector L MacQueen, *The Scottish Legal System*, Bloomsbury Professional, Haywards Heath, West Sussex, England, 2013, pp. 37.

⁷ For the purposes of this analysis, the legislation of England and Wales will be the main object of study.

⁸ White et al, op. cit., 2013, pp. 297.

⁹ White et al, op. cit., 2013, pp. 162-163.

incorporating legislation is enacted, the national courts have no power to enforce treaty rights and obligations either on behalf of the Government or a private individual.¹⁰

1.2 The UK and United Nations

The UK is a founding member of the United Nations and one of five permanent members of the UN Security Council.

1.3 The UK and UNESCO

The UK ratified the convention on 29 May 1984. Relevant (and indicative) texts: Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), Declaration on the Responsibilities of the Present Generations Towards Future Generations (1997), Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights (1997), International Declaration on Human Genetic Data (2003) and Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (2005).

1.4 The UK and OECD

The United Kingdom is a member of the Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) having signed the Convention on the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development of 14 December 1960.

1.5 The UK and the Council of Europe (CoE)

The UK was first joint signatory of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR). The Human Rights Act 1998 ‘embedded’ the Convention into the UK legal system, making the Convention directly applicable.

Despite its importance, the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine¹¹ has not been signed by the UK. The UK has not signed the Convention on the grounds that it considers it too restrictive especially as far as embryo experimentation is concerned.¹² It is worth highlighting that the creation of human embryos for research is permitted -under conditions- in the UK contrary to the prohibitive provisions of Article 18 of the Convention.

¹⁰ House of Commons European Scrutiny Committee, “Tenth Report-The EU Bill and Parliamentary Sovereignty”, 24 December 2010 para 2.10. <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201011/cmselect/cmeuleg/633/63302.htm>

¹¹ Council of Europe, Convention for the protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine ETS No.164.

¹² Andorno, R., “The Oviedo Convention: A European Legal Framework at the Intersection of Human Rights and Health Law” *Journal of International Biotechnology Law* 2, 4, 2005, pp. 133-143, pp. 134. See further Raposo, Vera Lúcia and Eduardo Osuna, “European Convention of Human Rights and Biomedicine”, in Roy Beran (ed.), *Legal and Forensics Medicine*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 2013, pp. 1406-1407.

Although the UK has not signed this Convention, it is argued that the UK has considered its provisions when legislating for the relevant issues.¹³ This Convention, as well as the non-binding instruments of UNESCO, have an impact on the production and interpretation of the UK legislation.¹⁴

1.6 The UK and European Union

The UK acceded to the European Community (now European Union – EU) in 1973. By virtue of Article 50 of the Treaty on European Union,¹⁵ the UK will exit the EU on 29 March 2019 and will no longer be subject to EU law, unless a deal is made that provides otherwise. This may create legal uncertainty and unclarity about the future legal developments in the field of genetics and genomics.

The possible impact of Brexit on the UK legal landscape and research is complex and somewhat obscure.¹⁶ For instance, with regard to research on animals the EU Withdrawal Act¹⁷ does not include any provisions to transfer the principle in Article 13 of the Lisbon Treaty recognising animals as sentient beings into UK legislation. The UK Animal Welfare Act 2006, does not explicitly recognise this concept and this has raised concerns,¹⁸ since this could further influence other regulatory systems, such as medical and biological research on animals.¹⁹ Moreover, concerns are raised regarding the relocation of the EMA, laboratories, recruitment of human resources and funding of research.²⁰

Although the Nuffield Council on Bioethics supports that ‘the extent to which the UK will retain provisions of EU law or be bound by the jurisdiction of its courts, though undecided at the time of writing, may attenuate significantly in the long term,’ it is of the opinion that the UK regulatory

¹³ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues,” 2018, pp. 116. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

¹⁴ Seatzu, F., “The Experience of the European Court of Human Rights with the European Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine”, *Utrecht Journal of International and European Law*, Vol. 31 No.81, 2015, pp. 5, 14.

¹⁵ See Article 50 of the Consolidated versions of the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union [2012] OJ C326/01.

¹⁶ Mills, P, “Brexit and bioethics”, 14 July 2016 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/blog/brexit-bioethics>; Laurie, Graeme, “How do we make sense of chaos? Navigating health research regulation through the liminality of the Brexit process”, *Medical Law International*, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0968533218799533>

¹⁷ European Union (Withdrawal) Act 2018.

¹⁸ House of Commons, “Animal Sentience and Brexit”, Briefing Paper number 8155, 8 August 2018 <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/CBP-8155#fullreport>

¹⁹ Home Office, “Animals in Science Regulation Unit Annual Report 2016”, 12 March 2018, pp. 13 https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/687251/asru-annual-report-2016.pdf

²⁰ House of Commons Select Committee on Health and Social Care, “Brexit: Medicines, Medical Devices and Substances of Human Origin”, Fourth Report, HC 392, 21 March 2018, pp. 30 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201719/cmselect/cmhealth/392/392.pdf>

framework will remain in alignment with the European one.²¹ In the same vein, the Health and Social Care Committee argues that the regulatory alignment with the European legislation should be an ongoing priority for the UK.²² The Government has confirmed²³ that UK law will remain aligned with the Clinical Trials Regulation (Regulation EU No) 536/2014.²⁴

In 2000, the EU adopted the Charter of Fundamental Rights, although it was not legally binding at that point. Pursuant to Article 6(1) of the Treaty on European Union, the Charter became applicable with the adoption of the Treaty of Lisbon on 1 December 2009. The Charter incorporates the whole range of civil, political, economic and social rights of European citizens, approximating the legal constitutions and international obligations common to Member States. It should be noted though that as far as the legal status of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union is concerned in the post-Brexit era, the Charter will remain part of the UK law.²⁵

2. Objectives of the report

In line with guidance issued in SIENNA Task 2.2, this report examines the UK's regulatory framework regarding genetics and genomics as specified for SIENNA Task 2.2. More specifically, it examines:

- Q 1 How, if at all, human germline gene editing is regulated?
- Q 2 Genetic screening in general
- Q 3 Genetic testing in general
- Q 4 Prenatal testing/screening
- Q 5 New-born screening
- Q6 Advertising of genetic testing or screening

²¹ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, "Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues," 2018, pp. 108. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

²² House of Commons Select Committee on Health and Social Care, "Brexit: Medicines, Medical Devices and Substances of Human Origin", Fourth Report, HC 392, 21 March 2018, paras 61 and 71 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201719/cmselect/cmhealth/392/392.pdf>

²³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/clinical-trials-regulation>

²⁴ European Parliament and the Council, Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC.

²⁵ Kentish, B., "House of Lords defeats government plans to scrap EU rights charter after Brexit", 23 April 2018 <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/politics/brexit-latest-eu-rights-charter-uk-government-house-of-lords-withdrawal-bill-a8318731.html>

3. Approach, materials and method

3.1 Literature overview

Regarding the discussed topics, academic literature is scarce.

The following terms were used as key-words for research: human germline gene editing, genetic screening, genetic testing, prenatal testing/screening, new-born screening and advertising of genetic testing or screening. In addition to this paucity of available resources, most literature does not address the legal aspects of genetics and genomics from a UK perspective in a comprehensive fashion.

3.2 Legal developments

To identify and present the legal development currently discussed and/or designed on a policy level in the UK, we reviewed the web pages of governmental and advisory bodies, institutions, authorities and UK based campaigning organisations.

3.3 Analysis of legislation for 6 specific questions

The applicable legislation is presented and analysed in each section. In interpreting the relevant legislation, official guidance and academic literature were useful tools.

4. Scope and limitations of the report

The above method was considered to be the best option to review, summarise and provide the research findings in a concise, comprehensive, and clear manner. We identified five main challenges in carrying out the SIENNA task while reviewing the existing legal and academic literature, official guidance issued by the competent authorities and soft law publications produced by UK based campaigning organisations in the domain of genetics and genomics, such as GeneWatch UK.

First, as already stated, there is a paucity of legal academic literature that specifically addresses the relevant legal provisions and issues from a UK point of view. Although, there is a prolific amount of literature and initiatives on genetics and genomics in the UK, most of the produced literature examines the (bio)ethical aspects – and least the hard-core legal issues – in a more international and European context under a *de lege ferenda* approach.

Second, another difficulty we faced while reviewing the available resources refers to the lack of a common understanding of the basic notions and terminology. There is no uniformity among legal scholars, the legislator, and scholars from other disciplines on the conceptualisation of the fundamental terms. Legal acts do not always use a scientific terminology and legal scholars tend not to fully understand genetics and genomics technologies. Legal academic literature tends to analyse the relevant framework in an inclusive manner, without discriminating between genetics, genomics and other technologies. On the contrary, all the relevant legal issues, which fall under the same legal acts, are examined together, such as reproductive technologies, cloning, genetic testing etc. Indeed, the terminology and categorisations employed by the legal scholars do not often coincide with the scientific terminology used in genetics and genomics. This augments the legal uncertainty about which procedures are permitted, restricted or prohibited. Moreover, although these technologies have raised legal concerns, they have been mostly examined from the perspective of data protection and privacy (genetic data), discrimination (genetic essentialism and the regulation in employment and insurance) rather than on understanding and assessing the legality of genetics and genomics technologies in a holistic manner. Third, there is not a comprehensive and overarching legal framework

across the UK. Fourth, there are no strict legal definitions of genetics and genomics practices under English and Welsh law, but such practices are defined on a basis of process or even result. Fifth, in light of Brexit, there is great uncertainty about future legal developments, as well as research and policy initiatives.

Part II

5. Current legal academic debates in the area of genetics and genomics

5.1 Current legal academic debates regarding human germline gene editing

As analysed in detail below, germline gene editing is restrictively permitted in a research context, whereas it is illegal to use genome editing on human cells and embryos for clinical purposes, such as for fertility treatments.

Overall, the main arguments against permitting human germline gene editing for clinical purposes are based on the slippery slope argument.²⁶ Nonetheless, there have been arguments in favour of permitting this practice and distinguishing between germline gene editing for eugenics and therapeutic purposes.²⁷

As explained below, germline gene editing is exceptionally permitted for research purposes under particular conditions. One of the most controversial and debated ones is the 14-day limit. Indeed, according to section 3ZA of the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act, as amended, a license for germline gene editing for research cannot authorise keeping or using an embryo after the appearance of the primitive streak. The Act provides that the primitive streak is to be taken to have appeared in an embryo not later than the end of the period of 14 days beginning with the day on which the process of creating the embryo began, not counting any time during which the embryo is stored.

There has been some criticism against this 14-day limit, with a view to reviewing and extending it. This provision has been partially challenged as arbitrarily drawing the lines between permissible and forbidden. It is argued that it is more a legal response to these technologies than relating to biological and genetic factors.²⁸

²⁶ Holtug, N., “Human gene therapy: down the slippery slope?”, *Bioethics*, Vol. 7, No. 5, 1993, pp. 402-19.

²⁷ Harris, J., “Is gene therapy a form of eugenics?” *Bioethics*, Vol.7 No. 2-3 1993, pp.178-187.

²⁸ Williams, B, “Types of moral argument against embryo research”, in Ciba Foundation Symposium (ed.) *The Ciba Foundation, Human Embryo Research: Yes or No?*, 1986, pp. 184-194 and Brock, D., “Is a consensus possible on stem cell research? Moral and political obstacles”, *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 2006, 32(1), pp. 36-42. See also Harris, J, “It’s time to extend the 14-day limit for embryo research”, *The Guardian*, 6 May 2016 <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2016/may/06/extend-14-day-limit-embryo-research>. See further Jackson, Emily, *Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016, pp. 678-679.

5.2 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic screening in general

Not identified.

5.3 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic testing in general

Not identified.

5.4 Current legal academic debates regarding prenatal testing/screening

Not identified.

5.5 Current legal academic debates regarding newborn screening

There is a debate about whether genetic profiling of babies at birth should be permitted in the public health context.²⁹ Although it may have significant benefits for health and research, there are several legal issues to be examined, such as privacy concerns and sharing genetic information, the storage and legal ownership of genetic material, patent issues, consent and reporting requirements, and safeguarding the autonomy of the future adult.³⁰ It has been suggested that new-born genetic screening should not apply generally, but it should be available and accessible based on its clinical utility and cost-effectiveness and the best interests of children.³¹

5.6 Current legal academic debates regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

Advertising of genetic testing, especially when it is directly addressed to consumers without the intervention of healthcare professionals, is a highly debated topic. Despite its complexity, no discrete legal framework applies in the UK. The Human Genetics Commission has issued guiding principles to promote high standards and consistency in the provision of genetic tests amongst commercial providers, but these principles do not supersede any national laws and should be used in accordance with the applicable international and domestic legislation.³²

²⁹ Human Genetics Commission, “Profiling the newborn: a prospective gene technology? A report from a Joint Working Group of the Human Genetics Commission and the UK National Screening Committee”, 2005 <https://web.archive.org/web/20111114141158/http://www.hgc.gov.uk/Client/document.asp?DocId=154&CategoryId=10>.

³⁰ For a comprehensive analysis see discussion in Taylor-Phillips et al., “The ethical, social and legal issues with expanding the new-born blood spot test”, 2014. https://www.google.co.uk/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0ahUKEwiG7MyC1JbZAhWpD8AKHcmMANKQFggnMAA&url=https%3A%2F%2Flegacyscreening.phe.org.uk%2Fpolicydb_download.php%3Fdoc%3D763&usq=AOvVaw3wW1zIBezi4okPx6mUPCIH. See also Wright, Caroline., at al., “Next Steps in the Sequence: the Implications of Whole Genome Sequencing for Health in the UK”, 2011 http://www.phgfoundation.org/documents/report_next_steps_Sequence.pdf.

³¹ Friedman, Jan M., et al., “Genomic newborn screening: public health policy considerations and recommendations”, *BMC Medical Genomics*, 10, 9, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12920-017-0247-4>

³² Human Genetics Commission, “A common framework of principles for direct-to-consumer genetic testing services”, 2010.

Initially, the terms of service of direct-to-consumer genetic tests are lengthy, using obscure and vague terminology, not understandable by the average service-user, and in a take-it-or-leave-it form.³³ Moreover, they fail to provide adequate information in clear and plain language about potential risks, benefits and limitations. Indeed, such agreements lack transparency and adequate information.³⁴ For example, they do not provide meaningful information about the reliability and utility of results, unexpected findings, potential risks for consumers and their family members and how these results can influence their lives. Even if the necessary information is disseminated, a huge amount of information is provided,³⁵ characterised by vagueness, obscurity and complexity.³⁶ States should provide for stringent legislation and accessible health services³⁷ based on the tenets of accountability, public reasoning and caution.³⁸

Therefore, there is an overall agreement on heavily regulating this kind of advertising, focusing on the need for informing about the potential risks and limitations of genetic testing, the utility and credibility of genetic testing as well as an agreement on restricting this advertising when directed to children.³⁹

5.7 Current legal academic debates regarding another topic not listed above that is very important to highlight in your country

Not identified.

<http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120504102236/http://www.hgc.gov.uk/UploadDocs/DocPub/Document/HGC%20Principles%20for%20DTC%20genetic%20tests%20-%20final.pdf>

³³ The Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology, “Consumer Genetic Testing”, March 2012, pp.4 <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/POST-PN-407>

³⁴ Hall, Jacqueline A, et al, “Transparency Of Genetic Testing Services For ‘Health, Wellness And Lifestyle’: Analysis of Online Prepurchase Information For UK Consumers”, *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 25, 2017, pp. 907-908.

³⁵ Bunnik, Eline M, Maartje H.N. Schermer and A Cecile JW Janssens, “Personal Genome Testing: Test Characteristics to Clarify the Discourse on Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues”, *BMC Medical Ethics*, 12, 2011, 8.

³⁶ Bunnik, Eline M., et al, “The New Genetics And Informed Consent: Differentiating Choice To Preserve Autonomy”, *Bioethics*, 2013, 27, 6, pp. 348-352.

³⁷ Tyler, C., “Liberalism and Communitarianism”, in Richard E Ashcroft (ed.), *Principles of Health Care Ethics*, John Wiley and Sons, 2007, pp. 37.

³⁸ See Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Emerging biotechnologies: technology, choice and the public good”, 2012 pp. 67-71 http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/Emerging_biotechnologies_full_report_web_0.pdf.

³⁹ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Medical Profiling and Online Medicine: The Ethics of ‘Personalised Healthcare’”, 2010, pp. 201-202. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/Medical-profiling-and-online-medicine-the-ethics-of-personalised-healthcare-in-a-consumer-age-Web-version-reduced.pdf>;

Human Genetics Commission, “A common framework of principles for direct-to-consumer genetic testing services”, 2010.

<http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120504102236/http://www.hgc.gov.uk/UploadDocs/DocPub/Document/HGC%20Principles%20for%20DTC%20genetic%20tests%20-%20final.pdf>

6. Legal developments in the area of genetics and genomics

6.1 Legal developments regarding human germline gene editing

In light of the promising genetics and genomics technologies, the UK aims to examine potential obstacles for innovation, including genome editing, and potential legislative amendments. It is suggested that any legislative amendments should be based on the legislative model of allowing mitochondrial donation,⁴⁰ as presented below. In practice, this means that Regulations can be enacted to amend the definition of ‘permitted’ egg and embryo based on section 3ZA of the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act, as amended, that states that: (5) Regulations may provide that: (a) an egg can be a permitted egg, or (b) an embryo can be a permitted embryo, even though the egg or embryo has had applied to it in prescribed circumstances a prescribed process designed to prevent the transmission of serious mitochondrial disease.’

Regarding genome editing for clinical purposes, the Department of Health and Social Care has stated that the Government has no plans to amend the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act to permit germline modifications.⁴¹ Additionally, the Government has clarified that there are no plans to amend the law to allow germline modification.⁴²

It is worth mentioning that the Nuffield Council on Bioethics has recently stated that human germline modification could be ethically acceptable in some circumstances, namely under the guiding principles of solidarity, social justice and welfare, so that the person born under this procedure will not suffer from negative consequences such as discrimination.⁴³ Nonetheless, any legislative change regarding heritable genome editing interventions is not currently urgent, and any amendment should follow public engagement and dialogue and the adoption of monitoring and safety mechanisms.⁴⁴

In 2015, in a joint statement on genome editing in human cells issued by the Academy of Medical Sciences and other leading UK research institutions, it was commonly agreed that genome editing

⁴⁰ House of Commons Science and Technology Committee, “Genomics and genome editing in the NHS”, Third Report of Session 2017–19 HC 349, Published on 20 April 2018 by authority of the House of Commons, pp. 51 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201719/cmselect/cmsctech/349/349.pdf>

⁴¹ Department of Health, “Written evidence (GNH0004) for Genomics and genome editing in the NHS” para 34. <http://data.parliament.uk/WrittenEvidence/CommitteeEvidence.svc/EvidenceDocument/Science%20and%20Technology/Genomics%20and%20genome%20editing%20in%20the%20NHS/written/71114.html>

⁴² Parliamentary office of science and technology, “Genome Editing”, POSTNOTE Number 541, November 2016 pp. 4. <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/POST-PN-0541>

⁴³ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues”, 2018, 136-138 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

⁴⁴ Ibid, pp. 134-137.

raises regulatory questions, but it ‘may hold significant potential for clinical application in the future’ and ‘there may be future potential to apply genome editing in a clinical context using human germ cells or embryos, although the distinction between germ and somatic cells remains crucial.’⁴⁵

The Wellcome Trust, the Association of Medical Research Charities and Cancer Research UK have recently argued that ‘the UK provides a robust but supportive environment for the use of genome editing in health. As genome editing technologies develop, regulation will need to keep pace to maximise health benefits while managing social and ethical concerns.’⁴⁶ They also argued that ‘the UK currently strikes a good balance with the regulation of genomic and genome editing technologies,’ and although there is not currently a case for amending the legislation, the UK framework is both robust and proportionate, responsive to technological developments.⁴⁷

The Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act, as amended, does not cover the case where ‘diploid sperm precursor cells (spermatogonia) are retrieved from a patient, edited in vitro using a genome editing technique such as the CRISPR-Cas9 system and returned to the patient’s testes (which may have been sterilised in the meantime to destroy any wildtype sperm and sperm precursors). If sperm production (spermatogenesis) were completed in the testes from these edited spermatogonia, this would, in theory, enable the patient to conceive a child with a partner through unassisted conception, with the result that the alteration could be transmitted via the sperm to the offspring. The reason this would not be caught by the regime of the Act is that none of the procedures contemplated involves a licensable activity within the meaning of the Act.’⁴⁸

It is worth highlighting that the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority (HFEA), which is the competent Authority for many genetic practices, as analysed below, is an independent and effective regulator. Its role is very important since it could allow innovative practices through the below described licensing system without the need for parliamentary involvement.⁴⁹ The Authority is

⁴⁵ The Academy of Medical Sciences and others, “Genome editing in human cells – initial joint statement”, 2015 <https://acmedsci.ac.uk/file-download/37773-55e6b4e90f49c.pdf>

⁴⁶ The Wellcome Trust, Association of Medical Research Charities and Cancer Research UK, “Written evidence submitted on Genomics and genome-editing: future lines of inquiry (GEN0038)”, January 2017, pp. 1 <http://data.parliament.uk/WrittenEvidence/CommitteeEvidence.svc/EvidenceDocument/Science%20and%20Technology/Genomics%20and%20genomeediting/written/46319.html>

⁴⁷ Ibid., pp. 2.

⁴⁸ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues”, 2018, pp. 104 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

⁴⁹ House of Commons Science and Technology Committee, “Government proposals for the regulation of hybrid and chimera embryos”, Fifth Report of Session 2006–07, HC 272–I, 5 April 2007, pp. 37-38 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200607/cmselect/cmsctech/272/272i.pdf>

encouraged to ‘take an approach to licensing similar to the one that it has taken with controversial applications of PGT and mitochondrial donation.’⁵⁰

For the first time in history, a license was granted by the HFEA to scientists at the Francis Crick Institute to apply CRISPR/Cas9 to modify genes in human embryos on 1 February 2016.⁵¹ The researcher used 58 embryos generated in fertility clinics as a result of in vitro fertilization (IVF) treatments. The embryos were no longer needed for IVF and were donated for research. The research team at Francis Crick Institute asked for a license for using CRISPR–Cas9 technology in embryos for early-development research. The HFEA granted a license for the genome editing of human embryos to examine possible causes of infertility. The findings reveal that human embryos need OCT4 to correctly form a blastocyst.⁵²

6.2 Legal developments regarding genetic screening in general

Genetic services in the UK are among the most comprehensive in Europe.⁵³ In July 2017, the Chief Medical Officer published a report, ‘Generation Genome’, which discussed the question of embedding genomic service provision in the NHS in England.⁵⁴ The same has been supported by the House of Commons Science and Technology Committee.⁵⁵ From October 2018 the National Genomic Test Directory will specify which genomic tests to be provided and commissioned by the NHS England.⁵⁶

6.3 Legal developments regarding genetic testing in general

Not identified.

6.4 Legal developments regarding prenatal testing/screening

Not identified.

6.5 Legal developments regarding newborn screening

The UK National Screening Committee advises the Government on NHS screening programmes. As discussed above in section 5.5, there is a debate about whether genetic profiling of babies at birth

⁵⁰ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues”, 2018, pp. 1138. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

⁵¹ The Francis Crick Institute, “HFEA approval for new genome editing techniques”, 28 January 2016 <https://www.crick.ac.uk/news/2016-02-01-hfea-decision>

⁵² Science, Media Centre, “Expert reaction to first UK results of genome editing in human embryos”, 20 Sept 2017. <http://www.sciencemediacentre.org/expert-reaction-to-first-uk-results-of-genome-editing-in-human-embryos/>

⁵³ Harris, R., “Genetic Services in Europe”, *Eur. J. Hum. Genet.*, 5 suppl 2, 1997, pp.1-220.

⁵⁴ Chief Medical Officer, *Annual report 2016: Generation Genome*, 4 July 2017 <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/chief-medical-officer-annual-report-2016-generation-genome>

⁵⁵ House of Commons Science and Technology Committee, “Genomics and genome editing in the NHS”, Third Report of Session 2017–19 HC 349, Published on 20 April 2018 by authority of the House of Commons. <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201719/cmselect/cmsctech/349/349.pdf>

⁵⁶ <https://www.england.nhs.uk/publication/national-genomic-test-directories/>

should be permitted in the public health context.⁵⁷ It is discussed whether genome sequencing should be employed to expand NHS new-born screening to include additional specific genetic conditions.⁵⁸

6.6 Legal developments regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

Not identified.

6.7 Current legal developments regarding another topic not listed above that is very important to highlight

Legal developments regarding pre-clinical research

There is an open discussion that the UK provisions about animal research are complex and bureaucratic.⁵⁹ In general, there has been criticism on the lack of openness about animal research in the UK.⁶⁰ In June 2001, the Animal Procedures Committee produced a report on biotechnology where it was considered that genetically modified (GM) animals did not need new legislation.⁶¹ In May 2001, the Royal Society produced a report on the use of GM animals which urged for public sharing of research findings, assessment and monitoring of the environmental impact.⁶² The Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council's position on research using genetically modified animals highlights the need for consideration of the relative benefits and costs of the application to society, the animals themselves and to the environment as well as the need for taking into account the wider social, technical, economic and political issues.⁶³

⁵⁷ Human Genetics Commission, "Profiling the newborn: a prospective gene technology? A report from a Joint Working Group of the Human Genetics Commission and the UK National Screening Committee", 2005 <https://web.archive.org/web/20111114141158/http://www.hgc.gov.uk/Client/document.asp?DocId=154&CategoryId=10>.

⁵⁸ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, "Whole genome sequencing of babies," March 2018 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/project/briefing-notes/genome-sequencing-babies/ethical-issues>

⁵⁹ House of Lords, Report on Animals in Scientific Procedures, 24 July 2002, pp. 42 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld/ldanimal.htm>

⁶⁰ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, "The ethics of research involving animals", May 2005, pp. 28-29 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/The-ethics-of-research-involving-animals-full-report.pdf>

⁶¹ Animal Procedures Committee, "Report on Biotechnology," June 2001. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/119029/biotechnology.pdf

⁶² See The Royal Society, "The use of genetically modified animals", May 2001 27-28 https://royalsociety.org/~media/Royal_Society_Content/policy/publications/2001/10026.pdf

⁶³ Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council, "BBSRC's position on research using genetically modified animals", July 2011. <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/documents/genetically-modified-animals-pdf>

Part III Specific legal considerations on human genetics and genomics

7. Human germline gene editing

Outline

The UK legislation does not provide for a comprehensive definition of basic research in human embryos and gametes using germline modification. Moreover, it is argued that the properties of genome editing and the relevant circumstances of the application of genome editing may blur the lines between applied and basic research.⁶⁴

The Warnock Report was the forerunner of the Human Fertilisation Embryology Act 1990 and the creation of the Human Fertilisation Embryology Authority in the UK.⁶⁵ The Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990 (Act) entails the legal provisions regarding research on human embryos and gametes. The Act provides for the use and storage of sperm, eggs and embryos for human application, as well as all research involving the use of human and admixed embryos. The Act was amended – and not repealed – by the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 2008.

The HFEA is the UK competent authority and regulator of assisted conception and human embryo research. The HFEA was established by Parliament in 1991 based on the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990 and constitutes the first of its type worldwide.⁶⁶ The HFEA, a statutory body and the first of its type in the world, plays an important role in regulating the activities which are germane to fertility clinics and research centres. The HFEA is responsible for various functions, such as regulating, advising, monitoring and licensing all UK human embryo research. In essence, the HFEA is responsible for ensuring that the creation and use of embryos and gametes in research meet the legal requirements. Its role is fundamental to genomics research since the power to license and permit genetic research lies within the HFEA's remit.

The 8th edition of the Code of Practice⁶⁷ issued by the HFEA – published in October 2009 and last revised in October 2017 – is the key instrument that complements the Act and provides detailed and comprehensible guidance on the licensing schemes for professionals. This Code is currently under

⁶⁴ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues,” 2018, pp. 131-132. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

⁶⁵ Department of Health and Social Security, *Report of the Committee of Inquiry into Human Fertilisation and Embryology* (‘The Warnock Report’), Cm 9314, July 1984.

⁶⁶ House of Commons Science and Technology Committee, “Government proposals for the regulation of hybrid and chimera embryos”, Fifth Report of Session 2006–07, HC 272–I, 5 April 2007, pp. 11 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200607/cmselect/cmsctech/272/272i.pdf>

⁶⁷ Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority, *Code of Practice*, 8th Edition, 2017 <https://www.hfea.gov.uk/code-of-practice/>.

revision.⁶⁸ The Code of Practice, although non-binding, specifies the criteria of granting a licence. The HFEA has been active granting and/or denying licenses shaping the regulatory landscape. Nonetheless, concerns have arisen regarding the independence of the HFEA.⁶⁹ The HFEA's budget is based on the licensing scheme and fees. Therefore, the Authority's sustainability is dependent on the number of granted, denied and revoked licenses.

The Act is built on a general prohibition of such practices and further exceptions to this general rule if a licence is granted by the HFEA. Such licences permit research on gametes or embryos (including supernumerary embryos donated by those undergoing IVF procedures and embryos created specifically for research). There is no legal definition of genome editing in the law. A commonly-acceptable definition of genome editing refers to the 'germline modification of nuclear DNA (in the chromosomes) that can be passed on to future generations.' Overall, this is the definition adopted by the UK Government in its response to the consultation on mitochondrial donation.⁷⁰ Given that the Act specifies the purposes for which research may be carried out rather than the procedure used, genome editing techniques is considered an acceptable practice to the extent that it is carried out in accordance with the approved statutory purposes.⁷¹

In the UK, application of genetic modification techniques on germline cells for reasons of basic research is permitted. As far as research in human or embryos/gametes using germline modification is concerned, the UK legislator has taken a stringent approach and set high standards and conditions, as analysed below. This prohibition is justified on the basis of the principles of medical law and ethics and the precautionary principle that aim to anticipate adverse effects in the long-term.⁷² Under the current legal framework, genome editing is restrictively permitted in a research context and the use of such material in humans or for treating patients is expressly prohibited.⁷³ Under the Act, it is illegal to use

⁶⁸ Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority, *Code of Practice*, 9th Edition, 2018. <https://www.hfea.gov.uk/media/2565/hfea-draft-code-of-practice-9th-edition-consultation-version.pdf>

⁶⁹ Pattinson, Shaun D., *Medical Law and Ethics*, Sweet and Maxwell, 2017, pp. 277

⁷⁰ Health Science and Bioethics Division, Department of Health, "Mitochondrial Donation Government response to the consultation on draft regulations to permit the use of new treatment techniques to prevent the transmission of a serious mitochondrial disease from mother to child", July 2014, pp. 15.

⁷¹ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, "Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues", 2018, pp. 102. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

⁷² Laing, Judith, et al, *Principles of Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2017, pp. 1073.

⁷³ On the contrary, the editing of somatic cells falls within the ambit of the Human Tissue Act 2004 that regulates matters relating to human bodies, organs and tissue for research and transplantation. The editing of somatic cells is regulated by the Human Tissue Authority (HTA). The clinical application of somatic cell therapies is an advanced therapy medicinal products. Thus, it is regulated by the HTA and licensed by the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency. Regarding stem cells, the HTA, the HFEA (when they are obtained from embryos), the Medical Research Council's UK Stem Cell Bank and its group, and the Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) are responsible for overseeing and regulating stem cell use. More specifically, the editing of somatic cells for basic research or clinical purposes is overseen by the HTA, established

genome editing on human cells and embryos intended for fertility treatments. On the contrary, genome editing can be used in humans where the genetic change cannot be inherited, or in embryos that are used in research with no intention of implantation.

The definition of embryos

According to section 1(1)(a) of the HFEA Act 1990, as amended, embryo means a live human embryo and does not include a human admixed embryo. According to section 1(1)(b) references to an embryo include an egg that is in the process of fertilisation or is undergoing any other process capable of resulting in an embryo. Any gamete or embryo that has been subject to the genome editing is not a 'permitted' gamete or embryo under the Act. This means that genetically edited embryos and gametes cannot be used in clinical fertility treatments.

General restrictions on embryonic research

It is illegal to conduct any research on human or admixed embryos unless specific exceptions apply. The notion of admixed embryos is defined in section 4A(6) Act and is analysed below.

The general restrictions are the following:

1. The 14-Day limit (s. 3(3) and (4) Act)

S. 3(3): A licence cannot authorise keeping or using an embryo after the appearance of the primitive streak

S. 3(4): For the purposes of subsection (3)(a) above, the primitive streak is to be taken to have appeared in an embryo not later than the end of the period of 14 days beginning with (the day on which the process of creating the embryo began), not counting any time during which the embryo is stored.

2. The research purposes

According to schedule 2 para 3A(1) a licence can be granted if the activity appears to the Authority—

(a) to be necessary or desirable for any of the purposes specified in sub-paragraph (2) ('the principal purposes'),

(b) to be necessary or desirable for the purpose of providing knowledge that, in the view of the Authority, may be capable of being applied for the purposes specified in sub-paragraph (2)(a) or (b),
or

(c) to be necessary or desirable for such other purposes as may be specified in regulations.

under the Human Tissue Act 2004. The clinical application of somatic cell therapies is regulated by the HTA and licensed by the MHRA, under the scope of the Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products legislation. The UK Stem Cell Toolkit is a regulatory tool for those seeking to use human stem cells for research.

According to schedule 2 para 3A(2) the principal purposes of the research project include:

- (a) increasing knowledge about serious disease or other serious medical conditions,
- (b) developing treatments for serious disease or other serious medical conditions,
- (c) increasing knowledge about the causes of any congenital disease or congenital medical condition that does not fall within paragraph (a),
- (d) promoting advances in the treatment of infertility,
- (e) increasing knowledge about the causes of miscarriage,
- (f) developing more effective techniques of contraception,
- (g) developing methods for detecting the presence of gene, chromosome or mitochondrion abnormalities in embryos before implantation, or
- (h) increasing knowledge about the development of embryos.

3. The source of embryos

According to Schedule 2 para 3(1)(a) an embryo could be created for research purposes. Additionally, the surplus of embryos produced for infertility treatments could be later used for research purposes. The HFEA has no mandate to overall restrict the creation of embryos for these purposes.⁷⁴

4. Desirability and necessity

According to Schedule 2 para 3A(2) for a license to be granted, research must be found to be ‘necessary or desirable’ for the above purposes.

5. All licence applications are evaluated by the HFEA Licence Committee. Prior to applying for a licence, it is necessary that researchers obtain approval from an independent research ethics committee. Researchers from the NHS can apply to the NHS research ethics committees. For all research taking place in the NHS in England and Wales the Health Research Authority (HRA) and Health and Care Research Wales approval procedure should be followed. If the research project is led from Northern Ireland or Scotland and involves NHS/HSC sites then a different procedure should be advised.⁷⁵

‘Many studies taking place in non-NHS organisations commissioned to deliver NHS services will have HRA Approval because of the NHS sites involved. Studies which are taking place entirely outside of the NHS may still need to apply for an ethical opinion from an NHS REC. Examples of these include Phase 1 studies in healthy volunteers, any study involving adults unable to consent for themselves requiring approval under the Mental Capacity Act (in England and Wales) or the Adults with Incapacity Act

⁷⁴ Laurie, Graeme, et al, *Mason and McCall Smith's law and medical ethics*, Oxford University Press, 2016, pp. 716.

⁷⁵ Integrated Research Application System, “NHS/HSC R&D Permissions”.
<https://www.myresearchproject.org.uk/help/hlpnhshscr.aspx#england-wales>

(Scotland) and studies involving human tissue where REC review is required as set out in Governance Arrangements for Research Ethics Committees.⁷⁶

In addition to this, in order to issue a licence, the HFEA takes into consideration the regulatory principles as included in its Code of Practice which underpin the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act. Alongside other requirements it is stated that Licensed centres must ‘ensure that all licensed research by the centre meets ethical standards, and is done only where there is both a clear scientific justification and no viable alternative to the use of embryos.’ This aims at ensuring that all research projects are scientifically sound and ethics-driven.

The UK policy framework for health and social care research also sets out principles of good practice in the design, planning and conduct of health and social care research.

In vitro derived gametes

In-vitro-derived gametes are ‘gametes or gamete-like cells derived from pluripotent stem cells in laboratory’.⁷⁷ The Act permits the creation of stem-cell derived gametes for research purposes but not for treatment. According to section 3(2) ‘no person shall place in a woman— (a) an embryo other than a permitted embryo (as defined by section 3ZA), or (b) any gametes other than permitted eggs or permitted sperm (as so defined).’ According to section 3ZA(2) ‘a permitted egg is one: (a) which has been produced by or extracted from the ovaries of a woman, and (b) whose nuclear or mitochondrial DNA has not been altered.’

Human admixed embryos

The above provided definition of an ‘embryo’ does not cover the case of human admixed embryos. Prior to this Act, there was legal uncertainty about the status of hybrid embryos, leading to insecurity about whether they could qualify as humans and, thus, fall under the application field of the Act. In a decision of 2003, it was held that the creation of hybrid embryos fell within the same ‘genus of facts’ as those created by IVF.⁷⁸ The HFEA had granted a licence for the creation of admixed human embryos in the belief that it acts within its statutory powers. This decision was later challenged in the courts on the grounds that the Authority had acted outside its powers, because these embryos are not human. Given that the parliament had enacted the amending act in 2008 before the case came to court, a permission for leave to apply for judicial review of the Authority’s decision to grant licenses was not granted.⁷⁹

⁷⁶ NHS Health Research Authority, “Non-NHS research projects”, Last updated 19 March 2018. <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/approvals-amendments/what-approvals-do-i-need/research-ethics-committee-review/non-nhs-research-projects/>

⁷⁷ Laing, Judith, et al, *Principles of Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2017, pp. 836.

⁷⁸ *R (On the Application of Quintavalle and CLC) v Secretary of State for Health* [2003] UKHL 13.

⁷⁹ *R (On the Application of Quintavalle and CLC) v HFEA* [2008] EWHC 3395 (Admin).

The amending Act 2008 inserted a definition of “Human Admixed Embryo” into the 1990 Act. Human admixed embryos are created for research purposes. The rationale behind this practice is that there is a scarcity of human eggs. Donating human egg can be time-consuming and uncomfortable.⁸⁰

According to section 4A(6) Act a human admixed embryo is defined as:

- (a) an embryo created by replacing the nucleus of an animal egg or of an animal cell, or two animal pronuclei, with—
 - (i) two human pronuclei,
 - (ii) one nucleus of a human gamete or of any other human cell, or
 - (iii) one human gamete or other human cell,
- (b) any other embryo created by using—
 - (i) human gametes and animal gametes, or
 - (ii) one human pronucleus and one animal pronucleus,
- (c) a human embryo that has been altered by the introduction of any sequence of nuclear or mitochondrial DNA of an animal into one or more cells of the embryo,
- (d) a human embryo that has been altered by the introduction of one or more animal cells, or
- (e) any embryo not falling within paragraphs (a) to (d) which contains both nuclear or mitochondrial DNA of a human and nuclear or mitochondrial DNA of an animal (“animal DNA”) but in which the animal DNA is not predominant.

Regarding the term ‘predominant’ there is no definition in law as to the meaning of this concept. In October 2008, the House of Lords Parliamentary Under-Secretary of State in the Department of Health, Lord Darzi argued that, “If it were considered that an embryo was to be created in which the human DNA would ultimately predominate, an application for an admixed research license would have to be made to the HFEA at the outset. This is because a license is required to bring about the creation of a human admixed embryo. If a researcher was intending to create an embryo that would at some stage be predominantly human, for however short that time might be, they would need a license to do so.”⁸¹ Human admixed embryos are 99.9% human and are created for research and not for reproduction.⁸² The placing of admixed embryos in either a human (subsection 4A(1)) or an animal (subsection 4A(4)) is prohibited. Research on hybrid embryos also falls under the general restrictions applicable to human embryos used in research. Consent is required from the person donating embryos, gametes or cells to create human admixed embryos for research purposes.

Mitochondrial donation

⁸⁰ Jackson, Emily, *Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016, pp. 673.

⁸¹ Lords Hansard, 29 October 2008, Column 1624.

⁸² Laing, Judith, et al, *Principles of Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2017, pp. 840.

The UK is the first country to provide for licensing mitochondrial donation.⁸³ The Human Fertilisation and Embryology (Mitochondrial Donation) Regulations 2015 rendered the practice of making deliberate biological changes that may be inherited by future generations legal.⁸⁴

During the parliamentary debates it became clear that the discussion was focused on distinguishing between cell reconstruction and altering the sequence of bases in a nuclear DNA molecule, namely between ‘germ line modification’ and ‘genetic modification.’⁸⁵ In accordance with the definition of genetic modification adopted by the UK Government, mitochondrial donation does not qualify as genetic modification. On the basis of that working definition, the Government’s view is that the proposed mitochondrial donation techniques do not constitute genetic modification.⁸⁶

The basis of this approach was that, in mitochondrial donation, the modification would be at the level of substituting whole subcellular structures (pronuclei or maternal spindles), rather than deliberately altering the sequence of bases comprising any DNA molecules.⁸⁷ This working definition and approach to distinguishing between the mitochondrial genome and the nuclear genome have raised doubts about its validity⁸⁸ and safety concerns.⁸⁹

In practice, with the mitochondrial donation – often referred to as ‘3-parent IVF’ health embryos can be created by using a woman’s eggs, her partner’s sperm and health donated mitochondria. This method refers to ‘an artificial reproduction procedure aimed at avoiding diseases transmitted by mitochondria. The disease is only transmitted by the mother, via the defective mitochondria in the oocyte. Mitochondria are small ‘energy factories’, present in every cell of the body, carrying mitochondrial DNA, which accounts for 1% of the total human genome.’⁹⁰ Any modifications to the

⁸³ Ibid., pp. 777.

⁸⁴ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues”, 2018, pp. 103. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

⁸⁵ Ibid, pp. 136.

⁸⁶ Department of Health, “Mitochondrial Donation Government response to the consultation on draft regulations to permit the use of new treatment techniques to prevent the transmission of a serious mitochondrial disease from mother to child, 15 July 2014. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/332881/Consultation_response.pdf

⁸⁷ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues”, 2018, pp. 103. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

⁸⁸ Scott, R., and S. Wilkinson, “Germline Genetic Modification and Identity: the Mitochondrial and Nuclear Genomes”, *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, 37, no. 4, 2017, pp. 886-915.

⁸⁹ Appleby, J. B., “The ethical challenges of the clinical introduction of mitochondrial replacement techniques”, *Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy*, 18, 4, 2015, pp. 501-514.

⁹⁰ Alliance Vita, “New genetic technologies in human beings and Human rights”, 2017, pp. 8. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKewjSs4>

genome (by the mitochondrial DNA) are transmissible by the mother to future generations.⁹¹ Schedule 3 of the Act provides for the necessary consent and information requirements. This consent can be withdrawn at any time until the embryo has been used for training people in embryo techniques.

Reproductive cloning

The Act is based on the notion of ‘permitted embryo.’ It does not include a hybrid embryo. The ‘permitted embryo’ can only be transferred into the woman’s body. This means that reproductive cloning is not permitted under the Act. The Human Reproductive Cloning Act 2001 was repealed by the Act.

8. Genetic screening in general

The State plays a crucial role in taking measures and decisions to prevent, eradicate and minimise harms to citizens and society at large. In this regard, the state has a legitimate interest in the public health care. The UK National Screening Committee (NSC) was founded in 1996 to appraise proposals for screening programmes, examine evidence for screening programmes and implement and monitor the impact of approved programmes, including genetic screening. In the UK, there are no population genetic screening programmes for adults.⁹²

9. Genetic testing in general

Genetic testing for health and health-related (lifestyle) purposes

There is limited hard information available about the size of the market of genetic testing directly targeted at consumers.⁹³ These tests include predictive tests medical treatment, pharmacogenetics tests, nutrigenomics and ancestry tests.⁹⁴ The proposed taxonomy of genetic tests available to consumers includes diagnostic, pre-symptomatic, carrier, pharmacogenetic, susceptibility, lifestyle/behavioural, phenotype, genetic-relatedness, genetic matching and ancestry tests.⁹⁵ These

[vU-t3dAhVID8AKHQgzAc0QFjAAegQIBRAC&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.alliancevita.org%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2017%2F04%2F2017-4-VITA-New-genetic-technologies-in-human-beings-and-Human-rights-site.pdf&usg=AOvVaw0Amaq9TVYGLZ8bqjmgAFCbZ](https://www.alliancevita.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/2017-4-VITA-New-genetic-technologies-in-human-beings-and-Human-rights-site.pdf&usg=AOvVaw0Amaq9TVYGLZ8bqjmgAFCbZ)

⁹¹ Ibid, pp. 9.

⁹² Laurie, Graeme, et al, *Mason and McCall Smith's law and medical ethics*, Oxford University Press, 2016, pp. 260

⁹³ Wright, Caroline F., & Shelley Gregory-Jones, “Size of the direct-to-consumer genomic testing market”, *Genetics in Medicine*, volume 12, 2010, pp. 594. <https://www.nature.com/articles/gim201097>

⁹⁴ The Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology, “Consumer Genetic Testing”, March 2012, pp. 1 <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/POST-PN-407>

⁹⁵ Human Genetics Commission, “A common framework of principles for direct to consumer genetic testing services - Principles and Consultation Questions”, 2009, pp. 5-6.

tests cover a broad spectrum of purposes and a strict categorization is not feasible. The blurring line between health-related, recreational and educational purposes is obvious.

There is no overarching regulatory system relating to direct-to-consumer genetic tests. For example, consent for obtaining a biological sample is necessary under the Human Tissue Act 2004. The Human Tissue Act 2004 is the legal framework applicable in England, Wales and Northern Ireland.⁹⁶ The Human Tissue Act 2004 regulates the storage and use of human organs and tissue from the living, and the removal, storage and use of tissue and organs from the deceased, for health-related purposes.

This Act aims to ensure that appropriate consent is in place to enable the lawful retention and use of body parts, organs and tissue, for ‘scheduled purposes’, which include certain types of health-related research. The Act also prohibits certain forms of DNA analysis without consent throughout the UK. Indeed, according to section 45(1) Human Tissue Act ‘a person commits an offence if—(a)he has any bodily material intending—(i)that any human DNA in the material be analysed without qualifying consent, and (ii)that the results of the analysis be used otherwise than for an excepted purpose, (b)the material is not of a kind excepted under subsection (2), and (c)he does not reasonably believe the material to be of a kind so excepted.’ Nonetheless, there are no specific provisions about an identification mechanism of ensuring that the consumer purchasing the test is the same person, whose genetic material is analysed.⁹⁷

If a genetic test is a medical one, then medical genetic tests fall under the broader regulatory framework associated with medical devices in the UK. The licensing of medical devices is also governed by European legislation,⁹⁸ which has been consolidated in the UK.⁹⁹ Medical devices should be approved by Notified Bodies registered in member states. They are independent certification private bodies, assigned delegated regulatory powers. In the UK the MHRA is responsible for appointing UK Notified Bodies and monitoring their compliance with the applicable legislation. According to a different approach, the above framework applies to the test kits sent to the customer to produce the saliva sample, but not to the tests themselves or to the interpretation of the results.¹⁰⁰

The European Union (EU)’s In Vitro Diagnostics (IVD) Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (of 5 April 2017) regulates the placing on the market in the EU of “in vitro” medical devices. IVD devices include software (health apps) and genetic tests, which examine specimens from the human body to seek to predict or

⁹⁶ The Human Tissue (Scotland) Act 2006 applies to Scotland. Overall, the key-principles are the same but authorisation process and scheme differ.

⁹⁷ Jackson, Emily, *Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016, pp. 467.

⁹⁸ See Council Directive of 20 June 1990 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to active implantable medical devices (90/385/EEC) [1990] *OJ L* 189/17, Council Directive 93/42/EEC of 14 June 1993 concerning medical devices [1993] *OJ L* 169/1 and Directive 98/79/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 1998 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices [1998] *OJ L* 331/1.

⁹⁹ Medical Devices Regulations 2002.

¹⁰⁰ House of Lords Science and Technology Committee, “Genomic Medicine”, 2nd Report of Session 2008–09, pp. 68. <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld200809/ldselect/ldsctech/107/10702.htm>

diagnose disease. If genetic test results (specific tests, or whole genomes) are used for a medical purpose, these will also be covered by the IVD Regulation. The Regulation enters into force by 26 May 2022.

Family Law

Paternity tests are required as evidence in court. They will have to be carried out following specific court directions, which will name a specific accredited company to carry out the tests and to provide a report. Samples must be taken by healthcare professionals. Paternity tests fall under various legal instruments, such as the Family Law Reform Act 1969 (s20, 21 and 23), Family Law Act 1986 (s55A) and the Human Tissue Act 2004.

Immigration purposes

Paternity tests may be necessary to prove a biological relationship between an applicant and a UK citizen when applying to join family members in the UK under the amended British Nationality (Proof of Paternity) Regulations 2006.

Genetic testing for law enforcement purposes

The Protection of Freedoms Act 2012 came into force on 31 October 2013. Sections 1 to 25 of the Act cover DNA analysis retention. This legislation was enacted following the 2008 judgment of the European Court of Human Rights in the case of *S and Marper v UK*, where the ‘blanket’ retention of DNA profiles of innocent people violated the right to private life.¹⁰¹

10. Prenatal testing/screening

Preimplantation genetic diagnosis (PGD)

Preimplantation genetic diagnosis refers to ‘genetically testing a cell or two after removal from an early embryo.’¹⁰² During the cell division of a newly fertilized egg, it is possible to remove one or two cells for testing for genetic abnormalities. PGD is a special type of in-vitro fertilization (IVF) where the embryos created through the IVF process are tested for a specific genetic condition. Only those embryos without the condition are then used in the IVF treatment to establish a pregnancy. The option of PGD can be offered to couples who are at risk of having a child with a specific serious genetic condition regardless of any fertility difficulties. This is a time-consuming and complex procedure and not widely applied in the UK. Couples could receive funding from the NHS.¹⁰³

¹⁰¹ *S. and Marper v. The United Kingdom*, nos. 30562/04 and 30566/04 (ECtHR, 4 December 2008).

¹⁰² Pattinson, Shaun D., *Medical Law and Ethics*, Sweet and Maxwell, 2017, pp. 297.

¹⁰³ Jackson, Emily, *Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016, pp. 849.

Under the amended Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990 sch. 2 para 1ZA, a license is required for testing an embryo for one of following purposes:

- (a) establishing whether the embryo has a gene, chromosome or mitochondrion abnormality that may affect its capacity to result in a live birth,
- b) in a case where there is a particular risk that the embryo may have any gene, chromosome or mitochondrion abnormality, establishing whether it has that abnormality or any other gene, chromosome or mitochondrion abnormality,
- (c) in a case where there is a particular risk that any resulting child will have or develop—
 - (i) a gender-related serious physical or mental disability,
 - (ii) a gender-related serious illness, or
 - (iii) any other gender-related serious medical condition,establishing the sex of the embryo.

Where PGD is carried out people seeking treatment should be offered genetic counselling.

Sex selection

According to sch. 2 para 1ZB of the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990, as amended, practices designed to secure that any resulting child will be of one sex rather than the other are not permitted unless a license has been granted for the above reasons. In addition to this exception, such an authorisation can be granted where there is a risk that a woman will give birth to a child who will have or develop—(a) a gender-related serious physical or mental disability, (b) a gender-related serious illness, or (c) any other gender-related serious medical condition. For the purpose of this Act, illness or other medical condition is gender-related if the competent licensing authority is satisfied that—(a) it affects only one sex, or (b) it affects one sex significantly more than the other. Therefore, PGD is permitted for conditions such as breast cancer gender-related physical or mental disease but not for social reasons.¹⁰⁴

Arguments in favour of sex selection have been expressed.¹⁰⁵

Tissue-typing

¹⁰⁴ Laing, Judith, et al, *Principles of Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2017, pp. 847.

¹⁰⁵ In favour of sex selection: Steinbock, B., "Sex selection: not obviously wrong", *Hastings Cent Rep Hastings*, 32(1), 2002 Jan-Feb, pp. 23-8 and Harris, J., "Sex selection and regulated hatred", *J Med Ethics*, 31, 2005, pp. 291-4.

Pre-implantation tissue typing (PTT), known as ‘saviour siblings’, is a procedure that involves taking a cell from an early embryo and testing it to assess whether the resulting child would be a good tissue match for a sick sibling.¹⁰⁶

Prior to the 2008 amendments of the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990, it had been held that the practice of permitting cell nuclear replacement fell under the scope of the Act and that it could be licensed based on a comprehensive and purposive interpretation of the Act.¹⁰⁷ According to sch. 2 para 1ZA (1)(d) Act a license is required: in a case where a person (“the sibling”) who is the child of the persons whose gametes are used to bring about the creation of the embryo (or of either of those persons) suffers from a serious medical condition which could be treated by umbilical cord blood stem cells, bone marrow or other tissue of any resulting child, establishing whether the tissue of any resulting child would be compatible with that of the sibling. This practice has raised concerns about the objectifying humans and paving the way for germline modification.¹⁰⁸

Prenatal diagnostic genetic tests (amniocentesis and CVS tests)

These are diagnostic tests carried out on a pregnancy to check for a genetic condition affecting the developing foetus. They are offered when there is an increased risk that the foetus could have a serious genetic disorder. All pregnant women in England, Scotland and Wales are offered antenatal genetic screening for Down syndrome and neural tube defects and have the opportunity to terminate a pregnancy if ‘there is substantial risk that the child would suffer from physical or mental abnormalities as to be seriously handicapped’ (Abortion Act 1967 s. 1(d)).

Nonetheless, the Abortion Act 1967 does not extend to Northern Ireland. Sections 58 and 59 of the Offences against the Person Act 1861 and sections 25 and 26 of the Criminal Justice Act (Northern Ireland) 1945 provide for stringent requirements for abortion, where abortion is permitted only if the life of the woman, but not in case of fatal foetal abnormality. Based on the eighth amendment, a clause inserted into the Irish constitution restricting the abortion. This framework has been challenged by caselaw¹⁰⁹ and a recent referendum in May 2018, requiring legislative changes.

The Abortion Act 1967 was amended by the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990, which introduced a time limit of 24 weeks of gestation on the most common ground for abortion, which is that “the continuance of the pregnancy would involve risk, greater than if the pregnancy were terminated, of injury to the physical or mental health of the pregnant woman or any existing children of her family” (section 1(1)(a)). A further ground for abortion, which does not have a gestational time

¹⁰⁶ Jackson, Emily, *Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016, pp. 858.

¹⁰⁷ R. (*on the application of Quintavalle*) v *Secretary of State for Health* [2003] UKHL 13 House of Lords.

¹⁰⁸ For an overview see Sheldon, Sally, and Wilkinson, Stephen., “Should selecting saviour siblings be banned?”, *J Med Ethics*, 30, 2004, pp. 533-7.

¹⁰⁹ For a history of the relevant case law see Connolly, M-L., “Supreme Court rejects NI abortion law case,” 7 June 2018. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-northern-ireland-44395150>

limit, is that “there is a substantial risk that if the child were born it would suffer from such physical or mental abnormalities as to be seriously handicapped” (section 1(1)(d).

Non-invasive prenatal diagnostic (NIPD) tests

Non-invasive prenatal diagnosis (NIPD) or testing (NIPT) is based on a maternal blood test. NIPD is currently being offered through the NHS to determine foetal sex in pregnancies at risk of serious X-linked conditions, such as Duchenne muscular dystrophy, and those at risk of congenital adrenal hyperplasia. Testing requires a sample of blood, taken from the mother’s arm, as with a regular blood test.¹¹⁰

From 2018, women will be offered a safer screening test as an alternative to the invasive tests. A simple blood test will be offered which is then used to check for DNA fragments of these chromosomal syndromes. or Down’s, Edwards’ and Patau’s syndromes.¹¹¹

All health and social care providers in England, including private hospitals and clinics, must be registered and regulated by the Care Quality Commission if they carry out one or more ‘regulated activities’ as described in the Health and Social Care Act 2008 (Regulated Activities) Regulations 2014. All doctors, midwives and nurses working in either the NHS or the private sector must be registered with the General Medical Council or the Nursing and Midwifery Council.

The manufacture of NIPT tests in the UK is regulated by the Medical Devices Regulations.

11. Newborn screening

New-born screening¹¹² involves the identification of a baby’s risk of developing a disease that is preventable or treatable. The current new-born screening programme in the UK based on the blood spot test (heel prick, dried onto a piece of filter paper) screens for nine rare but serious conditions: sickle cell disease, cystic fibrosis, congenital hypothyroidism, phenylketonuria, medium-chain acyl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency, maple syrup urine disease, isovaleric acidaemia, glutaric aciduria type 1 and homocystinuria (pyridoxine unresponsive). New-born screening is not compulsory. In the UK, “parents are asked for verbal consent for new-born screening. They can decline for sickle cell disease, cystic fibrosis, and congenital hypothyroidism individually.”¹¹³ They can decline phenylketonuria, medium-chain acyl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency, maple syrup urine disease, isovaleric acidaemia, glutaric

¹¹⁰Great Ormond Street Hospital for Children, “Introduction to NIPD/NIPT: A guide for patients and healthcare professionals”, 2014. <http://www.rapid.nhs.uk/guides-to-nipd-nipt/introduction/>

¹¹¹Department of Health and Social Care, “Safer screening test for pregnant women”, 2 November 2016. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/safer-screening-test-for-pregnant-women>

¹¹² NHS, “Newborn bloodspot test”. <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/pregnancy-and-baby/newborn-blood-spot-test/>

¹¹³ Public Health England, “Newborn blood spot screening: programme overview”, Guidance, 2013, Last updated 2018. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/newborn-blood-spot-screening-programme-overview>

aciduria type 1 and homocystinuria as a group.¹¹⁴ The Human Tissue Act 2004 applies to this case as well.

According to the relevant Code,¹¹⁵ laboratories should retain all residual new-born blood spot cards for five years as part of quality assurance. 'Following this retention period, residual new-born blood spot cards will no longer be available and should be destroyed by the laboratory within 12 months. The five-year retention period begins from date of receipt of the blood spot sample in the laboratory.'

'The screening results form part of the child's medical record and will be kept in line with records management guidance.' The [Records Management Code of Practice for Health and Social Care 2016](#) sets out the retention periods for NHS organisations in England. According to the provided retention periods for screening activities, 'for child screening treat as a child health record and retain until 25th birthday or 10 years after the child has been screened whichever is the longer personal information is held.'¹¹⁶

12. Advertising of genetic testing or screening

The information that is provided to customers about genetic tests performed outside the NHS is not specifically regulated. The Advertising Standards Authority (ASA), the Office of Fair Trading (OFT) and the Office of Communications have overlapping responsibilities. Where complaints concern a device such as a genetic test, both the ASA and the OFT have said they would be likely to consult with the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) for further advice.

Therefore, the general legal framework applies, and all marketing and advertising must be an accurate

description of the product or service, legal, decent, truthful and honest. Under the Consumer Protection from Unfair Trading Regulations 2008 companies should provide information about the properties of the product in a manner which does not mislead consumers. Marketing communications should not either omit material information or be aggressive in terms of the transactional decision.

As far as the labelling of in vitro medical devices is concerned, Part IV of the Medical Devices Regulations 2002 provides that in vitro diagnostic medical devices must conform to the essential requirements set out in Directive 98/79/EC, and must be CE-marked according to one of the conformity assessment procedures set out in the Directive (regulations 36 and 40). According to regulation 35:

¹¹⁴ Ibid.

¹¹⁵ Public Health England, "Code of practice for the retention and storage of residual newborn blood spots", 1 January 2018.

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/670641/Code_of_Practice_for_the_Retention_and_Storage_of_Residual_Newborn_Blood_Spots.pdf

¹¹⁶ Information Governance Alliance, "Records Management Code of Practice for Health and Social Care", 2016, pp. 62. <https://digital.nhs.uk/binaries/content/assets/legacy/pdf/n/b/records-management-cop-hsc-2016.pdf>

Determining compliance of in vitro diagnostic medical devices with relevant essential requirements

(1) In determining which are the relevant essential requirements for a particular relevant device, and whether or not it complies with any of the relevant essential requirements, account shall be taken of its intended purpose.

(2) In order to meet the essential requirements set out in Section 8 of Part B of Annex I, the information to be provided under that Section must be in English if the device may reach a final user in the United Kingdom, unless— (a) the Secretary of State, to the extent that Directive 98/79 allows him to do so, has authorised the use of another Community language or more than one other Community language; or (b) the relevant device is a device for self-testing, in which case the instructions for use and the label must include a translation into the official language of any member State of the Community in which the device reaches a final user.

(3) A relevant device shall be presumed to comply with an essential requirement if it conforms as respects that requirement to a relevant national standard.

(4) A relevant device shall be treated as complying with an essential requirement in respect of which there is an applicable common technical specification only if it is in conformity with that specification or, if for duly justified reasons the manufacturer has not complied with that specification, an equivalent or higher specification.

13. Regulation of clinical research in humans

A. Clinical trials

The Medicines for Human Use (Clinical Trials) Regulations 2004 transposed the Clinical Trials Directive (Directive 2001/20/EC) into the UK legal order. Under:

Section 14(5): An application for an ethics committee opinion in relation to a clinical trial involving medicinal products for gene therapy, other than a trial falling within paragraph (4), shall be made to the Gene Therapy Advisory Committee.

Section 19(3): The licensing authority shall not authorise a clinical trial involving products for gene therapy if the use of those products in that trial would result in modifications to any subject's germ line genetic identity.¹¹⁷

¹¹⁷ Gene therapy include two types of gene manipulation, namely somatic and germline. Genome editing in somatic therapies is legal, but highly regulated under an ethical approval and licensing scheme. The Gene Therapy Advisory Committee (GTAC) is the UK national Research Ethics Committee (REC) for clinical trials of gene therapy according to regulation 14(5) of The Medicines for Human Use (Clinical Trials) Regulations 2004. All gene therapy products for the market butts be approved by the MHRA. The MHRA is responsible for regulating the use of

Under Regulation (EU) No 536/2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC, no gene therapy clinical trial may be carried out which deliberately results in modifications to the subject's germline genetic identity

B. Germline modification in another clinical setting

Genome editing under the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990, as amended, is restrictively permitted in a research context and the use of such material in humans or for treating patients is expressly prohibited.¹¹⁸ This means that any genetically modified embryos and embryos created by artificial gametes cannot be placed into a woman and that human reproductive cloning is prohibited.¹¹⁹

14. Pre-clinical research

A genetically modified (GM) animal is an animal whose genetic constitution has been modified applying genetic engineering. Genes could be moved from one species, including humans, to another. Moreover, genes could be also just removed. The most commonly used method of genetic engineering is microinjection that includes the injection of foreign DNA into a fertilised egg under a microscope.¹²⁰

In 2017, 3.79 million procedures were carried out in the UK involving living animals, where half of them were experimental procedures, whilst the other half were for the creation/ breeding of genetically altered (GA) animals.¹²¹ Most research on animals based on genetic engineering aims at increasing the knowledge on animal and human medicine, with rats to be the most commonly used animal in such activities.¹²² Genetic modifications on animal support both basic and applied research. They enable scientists to understand the function of genes, investigate the way that animals and organs function

medicinal products in clinical trials as well as for regulating the post-research marketing and use of medical products and devices.

¹¹⁸ On the contrary, the editing of somatic cells falls within the ambit of the Human Tissue Act 2004 that regulates matters relating to human bodies, organs and tissue for research and transplantation. The editing of somatic cells is regulated by the HTA. The clinical application of somatic cell therapies is an advanced therapy medicinal products. Thus, it is regulated by the HTA and licensed by the MHRA.

¹¹⁹ Laing, Judith, et al, *Principles of Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2017, pp. 775.

¹²⁰ House of Lords, "Report on Animals in Scientific Procedures", 24 July 2002, pp. 41 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld/ldanimal.htm>

¹²¹ Home Office, "Statistics of scientific procedures on living animals", Great Britain, 2017 (published 2018), pp. 6 https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/724611/annual-statistics-scientific-procedures-living-animals-2017.pdf

¹²² House of Lords, "Report on Animals in Scientific Procedures", 24 July 2002, pp. 41 <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld/ldanimal.htm>

and develop, for producing substances that will be later used in medicine and pharmaceuticals, and for xenotransplantation reasons, namely the transplantation of animal organs into humans.¹²³

Research involving animals is regulated by the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 (ASPA). The ASPA regulates procedures that are carried out on 'protected animals' for scientific or educational purposes that may cause pain, suffering, distress or lasting harm. The ASPA also regulates the breeding and supply of certain species of animals for use in regulated procedures or for the scientific use of their organs or tissues.

In order to transpose the European Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes, the ASPA was amended by the Amendment Regulations 2012 (SI 2012/3039).¹²⁴ Guidance on the interpretation, application and enforcement of the ASPA are provided in the Code of Practice for the housing and care of animals bred and supplied or used for scientific purposes and the Guidance on the Operation of the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986.¹²⁵ It is argued that the UK has the strictest system of regulation on research involving animals worldwide.¹²⁶

The amended legislation came into force on 1 January 2013. The ASPA is implemented by the Home Office in England, Scotland and Wales and by the Department for Health, Social Security and Public Safety in Northern Ireland. The Home Office is the responsible authority for enforcing the relevant legislation. Any research on animals requires a permission the Home Office. The Home Office is also responsible for monitoring the compliance with the law in cases of research on animals. In addition to the enhanced role of the Home Office, other bodies also participate in raising public awareness and advising on regulatory issues on pre-clinical research. For example, the Animal Procedures Committee is an advisory, non-departmental public body of the Home Office responsible for advising the Secretary of State on all issues regarding the involvement of animals in scientific procedures.

In case of breaching the below described license conditions, the ASPA provides for penalties.

According to section 18(2A)(c) ASPA, appointed inspectors report to the Secretary of State on compliance with the legal provision and conditions of the licences. Where there is non-compliance, under section 18(2A)(d), the inspectors must advise on the action to be taken by the Secretary of State. If the inspectors consider that the committed offence is sufficiently serious to justify referral for prosecution, such as in cases of animal abuses, they suspend any investigations pending referral of the matter to the prosecuting authorities.

¹²³ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, "The ethics of research involving animals", 2005. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/The-ethics-of-research-involving-animals-full-report.pdf>

¹²⁴ The Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 Amendment Regulations 2012.

¹²⁵ Home Office, "Guidance on the operation of the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986", 2017. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/guidance-on-the-operation-of-the-animals-scientific-procedures-act-1986>

¹²⁶ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, "The ethics of research involving animals", 2005, pp. 263 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/The-ethics-of-research-involving-animals-full-report.pdf>

According to section 22, ‘any person who carries on an undertaking involving the applying of regulated procedures to protected animals in contravention to’ specific provisions of this Act or any holder of a project licence who ‘(a) procures or knowingly permits a person under his control to carry out a regulated procedure otherwise than as part of the programme specified in the licence; or (b) procures or knowingly permits a person under his control to carry out a regulated procedure otherwise than in accordance with that person’s personal licence’ commits an offence.

Overall regarding the provided penalties for contravening the provisions of ASPA, there is a system of compliance notices, formal reprimands, retraining, revocation, suspension or amendment of licences, fines and imprisonment. The imposed penalty depends on the contravened legal provision. The severity of the breach and the degree of animal suffering are also taken into consideration.

It is necessary to highlight two important aspects regarding the penalties. First, these penalties can be imposed only to the extent that the regulated procedures under the ASPA are concerned. For example, the animal welfare legislation does not apply to killing a protected animal that has been set free or rehomed after completing the regulated procedures under the ASPA. Second, for the ASPA to apply an establishment licence holder must be subject to jurisdiction within the UK. In essence, an establishment licence holder must have either personal residence or company registration in the UK.

Definitions under the ASPA

Protected animal

According to section 1(1) of the ASPA, a ‘protected animal’ is ‘any living vertebrate, other than man, and any living cephalopod. Section 1(2) states that “any such vertebrate in its foetal, larval or embryonic form is a protected animal only from the stage of its development when— (a) in the case of a mammal, bird or reptile, [two-thirds of] 2 the gestation or incubation period for the relevant species has elapsed; and (b) in any other case, it becomes capable of independent feeding.” Section 1(2A) provides that “any living cephalopod in its embryonic form is not a protected animal.”

Living

According to section 1(4), a protected animal is living until its circulation stops permanently or its brain is destroyed. The ASPA qualifies a decerebrate animal as a protected living animal because its circulation is functioning, and its brain is not completely destroyed.

Regulated procedure

Section 2(1) provides for that a regulated procedure is “any procedure applied to a protected animal for a qualifying purpose which may have the effect of causing the animal a level of pain, suffering, distress or lasting harm equivalent to, or higher than, that caused by the introduction of a needle in accordance with good veterinary practice.”

Section 2(1A): A procedure is applied to an animal for “a qualifying purpose” if— (a) it is applied for an experimental or other scientific purpose (whether or not the outcome of the procedure is known); or (b) it is applied for an educational purpose.

Section 2(3A): The modification of an animal’s genes is a regulated procedure if— (a) the animal is a protected animal and the modification may have the effect mentioned in subsection (1); or (b) the animal is to be allowed to live until after it attains the stage of its development when it is a protected

animal and the modification may have the effect mentioned in subsection (1) after it has attained that stage (whether or not it is also likely to have that effect before the animal attains that stage). For example, ‘breeding mice with harmful genetic defects is a regulated procedure if you intend to keep the animals produced beyond two-thirds of the way through their gestation period.’¹²⁷

Section 2(3B): The breeding of an animal is a regulated procedure if— (a) the animal is bred from an animal whose genes have mutated or been modified or from a descendant of an animal whose genes have mutated or been modified; (b) the animal is to be allowed to live until after it has attained the stage of its development when it is a protected animal; and (c) after the animal has attained that stage the animal may experience pain, suffering, distress or lasting harm of a level mentioned in subsection (1) by reason of the mutation or modification referred to in paragraph (a).

Section 2(3C): For the purposes of subsections (3A) and (3B), references to the modification of an animal's genes include the modification before the animal comes into being of any genetic material by virtue of which it comes into being.

Research purposes

According to section 5C(3) project licence can be granted if the Secretary of State verifies that the project pursues one of the following purposes:

- a) basic research;
- b) translational or applied research with one of the following aims:
 - (i) the avoidance, prevention, diagnosis or treatment of disease, ill-health or other abnormality, or their effects, in humans, animals or plants;
 - (ii) the assessment, detection, regulation or modification of physiological conditions in humans, animals or plants; or
 - (iii) the improvement of the welfare of animals or of the production conditions for animals reared for agricultural purposes;
- c) the development, manufacture or testing of the quality, effectiveness and safety of drugs, foodstuffs and feed-stuffs or any other substances or products, with one of the aims mentioned in paragraph (b);
- d) the protection of the natural environment in the interests of the health or welfare of humans or animals;
- e) research aimed at preserving the species of animal subjected to regulated procedures as part of the programme of work;
- f) higher education or training for the acquisition, maintenance or improvement of vocational skills;
- g) forensic inquiries.

¹²⁷ Home Office, “Guidance on the Operation of the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986”, March 2014, pp. 10
https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/662364/Guidance_on_the_Operation_of_ASPA.pdf

Applying for a project licence under the ASPA restrictions

Overall, licenses are granted if:

- the potential results are important enough to justify the use of animals (the cost benefit analysis)
- the research cannot be done using non-animal methods
- the minimum number of animals will be used
- dogs, cats or primates are only used when other species are not suitable
- any discomfort or suffering is kept to a minimum by appropriate use of anaesthetics or pain killer
- researchers and technicians conducting procedures have the necessary training, skills and experience
- research premises have the necessary facilities to look after the animals properly

Pursuant to section 2A of the ASPA, the Secretary of State must exercise his or her functions to ensure compliance with the principles of replacement, reduction and refinement (the principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement)). More specifically:

- If other scientific methods of equivalent value are available that do not involve animals, then they must be used.
- The number of protected animals used should be reduced to a minimum
- The pain, suffering, harm and distress caused should be kept to a minimum.

Three licenses must be granted by the Secretary of the State before an experiment is carried out: a) a personal license for the individual doing the experiment, b) a project license for each experiment, and c) an establishment license for the institution undertaking the experiment. Licenses could be granted for medical, veterinary, scientific and environmental research. Each activity should be reviewed and authorised separately. For example, a ‘establishment in which genetically altered mice of a potentially harmful phenotype are bred under the authority of a project licence, must also be authorised as a breeding establishment if it also breeds genetically normal mice for use in procedures there or somewhere else.’¹²⁸

Projects must be approved by the Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Body, which also advises the principal investigator on matters relating to animal welfare and the he principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement). The project must then be approved by the Home Office. According to section 5B(3)(d) the Secretary of the State must ‘carry out a harm-benefit analysis of the

¹²⁸ Home Office, “Guidance on the Operation of the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986”, March 2014, pp. 17.

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/662364/Guidance_on_the_Operation_of_ASPA.pdf

programme of work to assess whether the harm that would be caused to protected animals in terms of suffering, pain and distress is justified by the expected outcome, taking into account ethical considerations and the expected benefit to human beings, animals or the environment.

Additional requirements apply to the use of endangered primates (ASPA Schedule 2B, para 1) and the use of non-endangered primates (ASPA Schedule 2B, para 2). In essence, the use of non-endangered primates can be licensed for basic research, translational or applied research or research aimed at preserving the species of primate being used. The use of endangered primates can be licensed for translational or applied research; or research aimed at preserving the species of primate being used. In both cases, a scientific justification is required on the fact that the purpose of project cannot be achieved by the use of non-primate animals.

15. Other

Whole genome sequences

The UK 100,000 Genomes Project¹²⁹ aims to sequence 100,000 genomes from around 70,000 people. Participants are NHS patients with a rare disease, plus their families, and patients with cancer by the end of 2018. The 100,000 Genomes Project was launched in 2012 and it is the first large-scale whole genome sequencing exercise in the world and aims to gradually support the integration of genomic medicine in the NHS.¹³⁰ NHS England intends to establish a Genomic Medicine Service, offering genetic tests ranging from analysis of single genes to whole genome sequencing as part of routine NHS care.¹³¹ The 100,000 Genomes Project uses a ‘broad consent’ model regarding data processing.

Gene drives

The UK is a world leader in the development of GM insect technologies.¹³² At the European level, the Directive 2009/41/EC and Directive 2001/18/EC are the applicable legislation. These directives have been transposed into UK law to create a set of national regulations. The Advisory Committee on Releases to the Environment, established under the Environmental Protection Act 1990, provides statutory advice on the risks to human health and the environment from the release of GMOs.

¹²⁹ UK 100,000 Genomes Project <https://www.genomicsengland.co.uk/the-100000-genomes-project/>

¹³⁰ The 100,000 Genomes Project Protocol v4, Genomics England v4 2017. <https://www.genomicsengland.co.uk/100000-genomes-project-protocol/>

¹³¹ NHS England, “Creating a genomic medicine service to lay the foundations to deliver personalised interventions and treatments”, Board Paper, 30 March 2017. <https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/board-paper-300317-item-6.pdf>

¹³² Science and Technology Select Committee, “Genetically Modified Insects”, 1st Report of Session 2015–16, pp. 30. <https://www.parliament.uk/genetically-modified-insects>

Genetically modified insects are produced by inserting new genes into their DNA. The aim of gene drive is to cause a gene to spread through a population at a greater rate than would be the case with natural inheritance. Researchers have discovered a way to accelerate the population-wide propagation of a trait by using a technique called a ‘gene drive.’¹³³ The main criticism against this framework is that the deliberate release directive had not been designed to cover GM insect technologies in mind, but it is rather an extension of the legislation for GM crops.¹³⁴

Forensic databases and law enforcement

The UK Home Office created in 1995 the world's first DNA database, the National Criminal Intelligence DNA Database to store the DNA of convicted criminals. Pursuant to Article 64(1A) of the Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984 DNA samples were collected and retained from any subject involved in a criminal proceeding, even if the subject was not convicted, but he or she was only a suspect. DNA samples were collected for crime prevention and detection purposes, rendering the UK's National DNA Database one of the largest worldwide and raising legal and ethical concerns about the legality and legitimacy of this system. The UK Government has responded to the *Marper* judgement, as presented above, by removing innocent persons' records from its DNA and fingerprint databases by virtue of the Protection of Freedoms Act 2012.

Biobanks

The UK Biobank is a major national and international health resource, and a registered charity in its own right, with the aim of improving the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of a wide range of serious and life-threatening illnesses – including cancer, heart diseases, stroke, diabetes, arthritis, osteoporosis, eye disorders, depression and forms of dementia. UK Biobank recruited 500,000 people aged between 40-69 years in 2006-2010 from across the country to take part in this project.¹³⁵

Overall, biobanks are a valuable resource for storing and analysing data and samples. Therefore, their activities are heavily regulated by several acts. In the UK the general framework on biomedical research and public health applies and no specific legislation has been enacted.¹³⁶ For example, the collection, storage and use of personal data is regulated by the Data Protection Act 2018 and the removal, storage, use and disposal of human bodies, organs and tissue is regulated by the Human Tissue Act 2004 and Human Tissue (Scotland) Act 2006.

¹³³ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing an ethical review”, 2016 pp. 79-82 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-an-ethical-review.pdf>

¹³⁴ Science and Technology Select Committee, “Genetically Modified Insects”, 1st Report of Session 2015–16, pp. 28. <https://www.parliament.uk/genetically-modified-insects>

¹³⁵ UK Biobank <http://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk/about-biobank-uk/>.

¹³⁶ Noiville, Christine, Florence Bellivier, Virginie Commin, “Biobanks for Research Purposes”, in Katharina Beier, Silvia Schnorrer, Nils Hoppe, Christian Lenk (eds.), *The Ethical and Legal Regulation of Human Tissue and Biobank Research in Europe*, 2011, pp. 35-50, pp.41

With regard to the UK Biobank, this biobank operates within the UK Biobank Ethics And Governance Framework, which sets out standards regarding the activities and research carried out by the biobank. It has no formal regulatory role, but it provides for data collection, security, anonymisation, confidentiality and sharing.

A ‘broad consent’ model is therefore adopted by many biobanks and was adopted by UK Biobank.

The Ethics and Governance Council ensures that any activities carried out by the UK Biobank are ethically sound. This independent Council also advises the funders and UK Biobank on governance relating to data collection and research.

Non-discrimination, genetic information and insurance

There is no specific legal act about genetic bias, discrimination and exceptionalism. The practice of taking discriminatory decisions and measures upon individuals’ status based on their genetic makeup falls under the general provisions of the Equality Act 2010 section 6(1)(b). Although account should be taken of establishing a regulatory framework tailored to address the concerns about genetic discrimination,¹³⁷ the government has argued that ‘at present, there is little, if any, evidence of discrimination against those who have a genetic predisposition, or that genetic testing is being used in a way which would give rise to such discrimination in the UK.’¹³⁸ The UK’s voluntary and soft-law regulation of the use of genetic data by insurers has proved to be flexible and responsive to changes in the genomic technologies.¹³⁹

The Government has an agreement with the Association of British Insurers (ABI), the UK’s insurance industry. This agreement regulates the way that genetic test results are used. Consumers are not forced to undertake any genetic test, but they may be asked to disclose any genetic findings as part of their medical records depending on the type of insurance services and products and the nature of the genetic test. More specifically, the results of a diagnostic genetic test should be shared with the insurer, whereas in the case of predictive tests consumers should disclose the results if they purchase a life insurance of more than £500,000 for Huntington’s disease.

Breach of confidentiality and genetic information

¹³⁷ Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues”, 2018, pp. 144-145 <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>

¹³⁸ Department for Communities and Local Government et al, “Discrimination Law Review A Framework for Fairness: Proposals for a Single Equality Bill for Great Britain”, 2007, pp. 133. <https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120919212654/http://www.communities.gov.uk/documents/corporate/pdf/325332.pdf>

¹³⁹ Chief Medical Officer, Annual report 2016: Generation Genome, 4 July 2017 pp.231. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/chief-medical-officer-annual-report-2016-generation-genome>

It is argued that an exception to the duty of confidentiality could be established on the grounds of public interest. Indeed, breach of confidentiality could be justified on the basis of anticipating and/or preventing a harm to a third party, who is genetically related to the patient.¹⁴⁰ The question of whether an obligation to share his or her genetic results with another family member for health or reproduction planning purposes has not been addressed by UK legislation. Nonetheless, a very interesting development refers to referring the question of the doctors' duty to share genetic information and findings to the court. In 2015, the High Court held that doctors neither owed a third party a common law duty of care nor breached Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights.¹⁴¹ The Court of Appeal unanimously reversed the High Court's decision and allowed the case to proceed to trial. In 2017, the Court opened the discussion that clinicians may owe a duty of care to a third party (daughter) based on the particular facts.¹⁴² The claimant (daughter) argued that clinicians knew that her father suffers from a genetic disease (Huntington's disease) and that she was pregnant, and although the father had rejected to sharing his genetic findings to her daughter, his clinicians were under a duty to inform her.

Part IV Discussion and concluding remarks

16. Human rights discourse and main findings

Based on the above findings and analysis it is reasonable to conclude that genetics and genomics have raised various concerns in the UK. Both research and clinical applications of human genetic material are heavily regulated. The UK has entrusted various competent authorities to apply and interpret the relevant framework, which has been proactively interpreted. Moreover, advisory bodies and research institutions raise public awareness, urging for public debates and legislative amendments.

Nonetheless, no clear conclusions can be drawn due to the complexity and over-inclusive character of these technologies, which cover wide areas of interest, including health, research and innovation. Another factor that should be taken into account is that there is a paucity of strictly legal literature in the UK. On the contrary, due to nature of the discussed topics, most academic publications attempt a more holistic and inclusive presentation and assessment of these technologies, including scientific, legal and bioethical considerations. What can be observed is that the UK aims to preserve its leading

¹⁴⁰ Ngwena, C., & R. Chadwick, "Genetic Diagnostic Information and the Duty of Confidentiality: Ethics and Law", *Medical Law International*, 1(1), 1993, pp. 73–95 and Laurie, G.T., "The most personal information of all: an appraisal of genetic privacy in the shadow of the human genome project", *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family*, Vol. 10, Iss. 1, 1 April 1996, pp. 74–101.

¹⁴¹ *ABC v St George's Healthcare NHS Trust* [2015] EWHC 1394 (QB).

¹⁴² *ABC v St George's Healthcare NHS Foundation Trust* [2017] EWCA Civ 336.

position in genetic and genomics and purports to extend their applications, by further embedding them into its national health system.

In terms of human rights, the discussed practices have raised several concerns. As depicted in the legal and academic literature, human genetics and genomics practices could challenge human rights and there is a need to ensure that the baseline of fundamental rights is protected. Legal and academic scholars have focused on the impact of such practices on the interests and human rights of individuals. The focus has been on considering and weighing the rights and interests of individuals and potential risks for society (i.e., unforeseen health risks and environmental problems) against the right to freedom of expression and thought of scientists and the concomitant prospect of scientific advancement and a better quality of life. In this regard, the rights to life, dignity, non-torture and respect for private and family life are significantly considered when examining the legal and ethical requirements and standards for human genetics and genomics. Furthermore, rights to intellectual property and the need for scientific progress and freedom of research are also taken into account. Moreover, the doctrine of consent is highly debated in the discussed topic. Consent is necessary to ensure the safeguard of the rights to bodily integrity, self-determination, privacy and data protection in case of genetic and genomic interventions. In the UK much attention has been paid to genetic information, genetic confidentiality, genetic bias and discrimination and consent requirements, rather than on genetic modification and engineering themselves. We have referred to most of the current UK topics in the above sections. With regard to the right to non-discrimination, there are widespread concerns that the discussed practices could reproduce or enhance bias against individuals based on their genetic characteristics, aggravating social inequalities. From a public health perspective, the right to equitable access to health care and research findings has been the focal point.

The upcoming Brexit further impairs legal clarity due to the alleged regulatory insecurity, as highlighted in the above sections. Most of the relevant discussions are held at a political level rather than at a policy level. Therefore, there is a need to provide clear advice, information and guidelines on what is legally permissible and not. In this context, the SIENNA task seems challenging and ambitious, but necessary to ensure the public's access to information and help governmental agencies, bodies and organisations to draw upon SIENNA comprehensive findings to assess the current framework.

17. Concluding remarks

This report provided a brief overview of legal developments and academic debates regarding human genetics and genomics in the UK. It addressed the particular legal questions and provided a brief description of the state of the art. In this regard, it also presented specific legal gaps, challenges and future attitudes regarding the given questions. The below conclusions should be read together with the above main findings.

Our main conclusions could be summarised as follows:

1. Genetics and genomics applications are heavily regulated.
2. Research is facilitated, while clinical applications are not. There is an ongoing debate about relaxing the requirements for genetics and genomics applications in a clinical context to support scientific progress and produce tangible benefits for individuals. Nonetheless, human rights concerns and the

risk of unanticipated consequences constitute barriers in relaxing the requirements for genetics and genomics applications for clinical purposes. This is in line with the general public attitude. The public in the UK is rather informed and positive about genetics and genomics technologies but it remains concerned about their unrestricted application for any reason, such as cosmetic changes and human enhancement.

3. The competent authorities and licensing systems have enabled a proactive application of the applicable legislation. This means that the licensing procedures of the regulated activities are a leeway in applying the stringent framework and tend to stimulate genetic research in the UK.

4. Many regulated activities, such as the advertising of genetic testing, fall under the generally applicable provisions.

5. In terms of future developments, the legal and political situation is quite uncertain and fluid.

References

1. Alliance Vita, “New genetic technologies in human beings and Human rights”, 2017. <https://www.alliancevita.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/2017-4-VITA-New-genetic-technologies-in-human-beings-and-Human-rights-site.pdf>
2. Andorno, R, “The Oviedo Convention: A European Legal Framework at the Intersection of Human Rights and Health Law” *Journal of International Biotechnology Law* 2, 4, 2005, pp. 133-143.
3. Animal Procedures Committee, “Report on Biotechnology,” June 2001. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/119029/biotechnology.pdf
4. Appleby, J. B., “The ethical challenges of the clinical introduction of mitochondrial replacement techniques”, *Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy*, 18, 4, 2015, pp. 501-514.
5. Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council, “BBSRC’s position on research using genetically modified animals”, July 2011. <https://bbsrc.ukri.org/documents/genetically-modified-animals-pdf>
6. Brock, D., “Is a consensus possible on stem cell research? Moral and political obstacles”, *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 2006, 32(1), pp. 36-42.
7. Bunnik, Eline M, Maartje H.N. Schermer and A Cecile JW Janssens, “Personal Genome Testing: Test Characteristics to Clarify the Discourse on Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues”, *BMC Medical Ethics*, 12, 2011.
8. Bunnik, Eline M., et al, “The New Genetics And Informed Consent: Differentiating Choice To Preserve Autonomy”, *Bioethics*, 2013, 27, 6, pp. 348-352.
9. Chief Medical Officer, *Annual report 2016: Generation Genome*, 4 July 2017. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/chief-medical-officer-annual-report-2016-generation-genome>
10. Connolly, Marie-Louise, “Supreme Court rejects NI abortion law case,” 7 June 2018. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-northern-ireland-44395150>
11. Department for Communities and Local Government et al, “Discrimination Law Review A Framework for Fairness: Proposals for a Single Equality Bill for Great Britain”, 2007. <https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120919212654/http://www.communities.gov.uk/documents/corporate/pdf/325332.pdf>
12. Department of Health and Social Care, “Safer screening test for pregnant women”, 2 November 2016. <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/safer-screening-test-for-pregnant-women>
13. Department of Health and Social Security, *Report of the Committee of Inquiry into Human Fertilisation and Embryology* (‘The Warnock Report’), Cm 9314, July 1984.
14. Department of Health, “Mitochondrial Donation Government response to the consultation on draft regulations to permit the use of new treatment techniques to prevent the transmission of a serious mitochondrial disease from mother to child, 15 July 2014. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/332881/Consultation_response.pdf

15. Department of Health, “Written evidence (GNH0004) for Genomics and genome editing in the NHS”.
<http://data.parliament.uk/WrittenEvidence/CommitteeEvidence.svc/EvidenceDocument/Science%20and%20Technology/Genomics%20and%20genome%20editing%20in%20the%20NHS/written/71114.html>
16. Federation of European Academies of Medicine, “Human Genome Editing in the EU”, 10 March 2017. <http://www.interacademies.org/File.aspx?id=31273>
17. Friedman, J.M., et al., “Genomic newborn screening: public health policy considerations and recommendations”, *BMC Medical Genomics*, 10, 9, 2017.
18. Great Ormond Street Hospital for Children, “Introduction to NIPD/NIPT: A guide for patients and healthcare professionals”, 2014. <http://www.rapid.nhs.uk/guides-to-nipd-nipt/introduction/>
19. Hall, Jacqueline A, et al, “Transparency Of Genetic Testing Services For ‘Health, Wellness And Lifestyle’: Analysis of Online Prepurchase Information For UK Consumers”, *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 25, 2017, pp. 907-908.
20. Harris, J., “Is gene therapy a form of eugenics?” *Bioethics*, Vol.7 No. 2-3 1993, pp.178-187.
21. Harris, J., “Sex selection and regulated hatred”, *J Med Ethics*, 31, 2005, pp. 291-4.
22. Harris, J., “It’s time to extend the 14-day limit for embryo research”, *The Guardian*, 6 May 2016. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2016/may/06/extend-14-day-limit-embryo-research>.
23. Harris, R., “Genetic Services in Europe”, *Eur. J. Hum. Genet*, 5 suppl 2, 1997, pp. 1-220.
24. Health Science and Bioethics Division, Department of Health, “Mitochondrial Donation Government response to the consultation on draft regulations to permit the use of new treatment techniques to prevent the transmission of a serious mitochondrial disease from mother to child”, July 2014.
25. Holtug, N., “Human gene therapy: down the slippery slope?”, *Bioethics*, Vol. 7, No. 5, 1993, pp. 402-19.
26. Home Office, “Animals in Science Regulation Unit Annual Report 2016”, 12 March 2018. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/687251/asru-annual-report-2016.pdf
27. Home Office, “Guidance on the operation of the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986”, 2017. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/guidance-on-the-operation-of-the-animals-scientific-procedures-act-1986>
28. Home Office, “Guidance on the Operation of the Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986”, March 2014. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/662364/Guidance_on_the_Operation_of_ASPA.pdf
29. Home Office, “Statistics of scientific procedures on living animals”, Great Britain, 2017 (published 2018). https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/724611/annual-statistics-scientific-procedures-living-animals-2017.pdf
30. House of Commons European Scrutiny Committee, “Tenth Report-The EU Bill and Parliamentary Sovereignty”, 24 December 2010 para 2.10. <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201011/cmselect/cmeuleg/633/63302.htm>

31. House of Commons Science and Technology Committee, “Government proposals for the regulation of hybrid and chimera embryos”, Fifth Report of Session 2006–07, HC 272–I, 5 April 2007.
<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200607/cmselect/cmsctech/272/272i.pdf>
32. House of Commons Science and Technology Committee, “Genomics and genome editing in the NHS”, Third Report of Session 2017–19 HC 349, Published on 20 April 2018 by authority of the House of Commons.
<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201719/cmselect/cmsctech/349/349.pdf>
33. House of Commons Select Committee on Health and Social Care, “Brexit: Medicines, Medical Devices and Substances of Human Origin”, Fourth Report, HC 392, 21 March 2018.
<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201719/cmselect/cmhealth/392/392.pdf>
34. House of Commons, “Animal Sentience and Brexit”, Briefing Paper number 8155, 8 August 2018. <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/CBP-8155#fullreport>
35. House of Lords Science and Technology Committee, “Genomic Medicine”, 2nd Report of Session 2008–09.
<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld200809/ldselect/ldsctech/107/10702.htm>
36. House of Lords, “Report on Animals in Scientific Procedures”, 24 July 2002.
<https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/ld/ldanimal.htm>
37. Howard H.C. et al., “Whole-genome sequencing in new-born screening? A statement on the continued importance of targeted approaches in newborn screening programmes”, *Eur J Hum Genet*, 23, 2015, pp. 1593-600.
38. Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority, *Code of Practice*, 9th Edition, 2018.
<https://www.hfea.gov.uk/media/2565/hfea-draft-code-of-practice-9th-edition-consultation-version.pdf>
39. Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority, *Code of Practice*, 8th Edition, 2017
<https://www.hfea.gov.uk/code-of-practice/>
40. Human Genetics Commission, “A common framework of principles for direct-to-consumer genetic testing services”, 2010.
<http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120504102236/http://www.hgc.gov.uk/UploadDocs/DocPub/Document/HGC%20Principles%20for%20DTC%20genetic%20tests%20-%20final.pdf>
41. Human Genetics Commission, “A common framework of principles for direct to consumer genetic testing services - Principles and Consultation Questions”, 2009.
42. Information Governance Alliance, “Records Management Code of Practice for Health and Social Care”, 2016.
43. Integrated Research Application System, “NHS/HSC R&D Permissions”.
<https://www.myresearchproject.org.uk/help/hlpnhshscr.aspx#england-wales>
44. Jackson, Emily, *Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2016.
45. Kalokairinou, Louiza, Pascal Borry, Heidi Carmen Howard, “Regulating the advertising of genetic tests in Europe: a balancing act”, *Journal of Medical Genetics*, Volume 54, Issue 10, pp. 651-656.
46. Kentish, K., “House of Lords defeats government plans to scrap EU rights charter after Brexit”, 23 April 2018. <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/politics/brexit-latest-eu-rights-charter-uk-government-house-of-lords-withdrawal-bill-a8318731.html>

47. Laing, Judith, et al, *Principles of Medical Law*, Oxford University Press, 2017.
48. Laurie, G.T., “The most personal information of all: an appraisal of genetic privacy in the shadow of the human genome project”, *International Journal of Law, Policy and the Family*, Vol. 10, Iss. 1, 1 April 1996, pp. 74–101.
49. Laurie, Graeme, “How do we make sense of chaos? Navigating health research regulation through the liminality of the Brexit process”, *Medical Law International*, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0968533218799533>
50. Laurie, Graeme, et al, *Mason and McCall Smith's law and medical ethics*, Oxford University Press, 2016.
51. Ngwena, C., & R. Chadwick, “Genetic Diagnostic Information and the Duty of Confidentiality: Ethics and Law”, *Medical Law International*, 1(1), 1993, pp. 73–95.
52. NHS England, “Creating a genomic medicine service to lay the foundations to deliver personalised interventions and treatments”, Board Paper, 30 March 2017. <https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/board-paper-300317-item-6.pdf>
53. NHS Health Research Authority, “Non-NHS research projects”, Last updated 19 March 2018. <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/approvals-amendments/what-approvals-do-i-need/research-ethics-committee-review/non-nhs-research-projects/>
54. NHS, “Newborn bloodspot test”. <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/pregnancy-and-baby/newborn-blood-spot-test/>
55. Noiville, Christine, Florence Bellivier, Virginie Commin, “Biobanks for Research Purposes”, in Katharina Beier, Silvia Schnorrer, Nils Hoppe, Christian Lenk (eds.), *The Ethical and Legal Regulation of Human Tissue and Biobank Research in Europe*, 2011, pp. 35-50.
56. Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “The ethics of research involving animals”, May 2005. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/The-ethics-of-research-involving-animals-full-report.pdf>
57. Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Emerging biotechnologies: technology, choice and the public good”, 2012 pp. 67-71. http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/Emerging_biotechnologies_full_report_web_0.pdf
58. Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Whole genome sequencing of babies,” March 2018. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/project/briefing-notes/genome-sequencing-babies/ethical-issues>
59. Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing an ethical review,” 2016. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-an-ethical-review.pdf>
60. Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Genome editing and human reproduction: social and ethical issues”, 2018. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/Genome-editing-and-human-reproduction-FINAL-website.pdf>
61. Nuffield Council on Bioethics, “Medical Profiling and Online Medicine: The Ethics of ‘Personalised Healthcare’”, 2010, pp. 201-202. <http://nuffieldbioethics.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/Medical-profiling-and-online-medicine-the-ethics-of-personalised-healthcare-in-a-consumer-age-Web-version-reduced.pdf>
62. Parliamentary office of science and technology, “Genome Editing”, POSTNOTE Number 541, November 2016. <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/POST-PN-0541>
63. Pattinson, Shaun D., *Medical Law and Ethics*, Sweet and Maxwell, 2017.

64. Public Health England, “Newborn blood spot screening: programme overview”, Guidance, 2013, Last updated 2018. <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/newborn-blood-spot-screening-programme-overview>
65. Raposo, Vera Lúcia and Eduardo Osuna, “European Convention of Human Rights and Biomedicine”, in Roy Beran (ed.), *Legal and Forensics Medicine*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 2013, pp. 1406-1407.
66. Royal Society, “UK public cautiously optimistic about genetic technologies”, 07 March 2018. <https://royalsociety.org/news/2018/03/genetic-technologies/>
67. Science and Technology Select Committee, “Genetically Modified Insects”, 1st Report of Session 2015–16. <https://www.parliament.uk/genetically-modified-insects>
68. Science, Media Centre, “Expert reaction to first UK results of genome editing in human embryos”, 20 Sept 2017. <http://www.sciencemediacentre.org/expert-reaction-to-first-uk-results-of-genome-editing-in-human-embryos/>
69. Scott, R., and S. Wilkinson, “Germline Genetic Modification and Identity: the Mitochondrial and Nuclear Genomes”, *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, 37, no. 4, 2017, pp. 886-915.
70. Seatzu, F., “The Experience of the European Court of Human Rights with the European Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine”, *Utrecht Journal of International and European Law*, Vol. 31 No.81, 2015, pp. 5-16.
71. Sheldon, S., and Wilkinson, S., “Should selecting saviour siblings be banned?”, *J Med Ethics*, 30, 2004, pp. 533-7.
72. Steinbock, B., “Sex selection: not obviously wrong”, *Hastings Cent Rep Hastings*, 32(1), 2002 Jan-Feb, pp. 23-8
73. Taylor-Phillips et al., “The ethical, social and legal issues with expanding the new-born blood spot test”, 2014.
74. The Academy of Medical Sciences and others, “Genome editing in human cells – initial joint statement”, 2015. <https://acmedsci.ac.uk/file-download/37773-55e6b4e90f49c.pdf>
75. The Francis Crick Institute, “HFEA approval for new genome editing techniques”, 28 January 2016 <https://www.crick.ac.uk/news/2016-02-01-hfea-decision>
76. The Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology, “Consumer Genetic Testing”, March 2012. <https://researchbriefings.parliament.uk/ResearchBriefing/Summary/POST-PN-407>
77. The Royal Society, “The use of genetically modified animals”, May 2001. https://royalsociety.org/~media/Royal_Society_Content/policy/publications/2001/10026.pdf
78. The Wellcome Trust, Association of Medical Research Charities and Cancer Research UK, “Written evidence submitted on Genomics and genome-editing: future lines of inquiry (GEN0038)”, January 2017. <http://data.parliament.uk/WrittenEvidence/CommitteeEvidence.svc/EvidenceDocument/Science%20and%20Technology/Genomics%20and%20genomeediting/written/46319.html>
79. Tyler, Colin, “Liberalism and Communitarianism”, in Richard E Ashcroft (ed.), *Principles of Health Care Ethics*, John Wiley and Sons, 2007.
80. US National Library of Medicine, “What is genetic testing,” 20 Nov 2018. <https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/genetic-testing>
81. White, Robin M., Ian D. Willock, and Hector L MacQueen, *The Scottish Legal System*, Bloomsbury Professional, Haywards Heath, West Sussex, England, 2013.

82. Williams, B., "Types of moral argument against embryo research", in Ciba Foundation Symposium (ed.) *The Ciba Foundation, Human Embryo Research: Yes or No?*, 1986, pp. 184-194.
83. Wright, Caroline F., & Shelley Gregory-Jones, "Size of the direct-to-consumer genomic testing market", *Genetics in Medicine*, volume 12, 2010.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/gim201097>

Cases

ABC v St George's Healthcare NHS Foundation Trust [2017] EWCA Civ 336

ABC v St George's Healthcare NHS Trust [2015] EWHC 1394 (QB)

R (On the Application of Quintavalle and CLC) v HFEA [2008] EWHC 3395 (Admin)

R (On the Application of Quintavalle and CLC) v Secretary of State for Health [2003] UKHL 13

R. (on the application of Quintavalle) v Secretary of State for Health [2003] UKHL 13 House of Lords

S. and Marper v. The United Kingdom, nos. 30562/04 and 30566/04 (ECtHR, 4 December 2008)